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Executive Summary

This report (Deliverable 3.3) presents the FIERCE project's findings on **feminist democratic innovations** from a bottom-up perspective. It offers strategies and tools that feminist movements in Europe can use to promote democratic alternatives and build intersectional alliances in times where democracy is challenged. The report also critically evaluates the capacity of these practices to revitalize democratic processes, highlighting the risks of reproducing exclusion and power imbalances. In line with FIERCE's focus, the report examines how feminist movements promote counterpublics and generate feminist knowledge in collaboration with feminist actors by embracing intersectionality, solidarity, understanding power dynamics, and engaging emotions as key elements of democratic innovation. Less attention is given to 'traditional' political science-driven interpretations of democratic innovations understood as gender representation and/or electoral regulations. The report's empirical findings are derived from the FIERCE Labs and FIERCE Actions, which engaged in bottom-up democratic processes of co-creation at national and transnational scales, in addition to interviews with politicians, civil society actors, and activists.

The **National and Transnational co-creation Labs** offer hybrid, invited spaces for democratic dialogue between academia and activism, and co-creative settings for knowledge production, striving to avoid intellectual extractivism and the exploitation of activists for academic purposes. With awareness and recognition of existing power relations and imbalances, the Labs challenge hierarchies that prioritize academic knowledge over activism. The FIERCE Labs served to promote gender equality and support feminist political agendas, guided by the collective effort to advance intersectionality. The focus on co-created knowledge production to sustain political mobilizations benefits from more strategic thinking, co-creating evidence for feminist claims, sharing emotions, strengthening alliances, and nurturing joint action. Across the FIERCE Labs, emotions included hope, resilience, frustration, and concern about the state of democracy. The emotional dynamics highlighted the FIERCE Labs as spaces of both intersectional solidarity and collective action, despite participants facing personal and collective right-wing and anti-gender mobilizations, politics, and attacks. Hope and enthusiasm grew from dialogue, alliances, collective resilience, and efforts to counter anti-gender backlash. Co-creation should be seen as both a method and a practice that requires dedicated financial resources to fairly value time, knowledge, and labour. The FIERCE Labs highlight the structural issue in Horizon Europe funding, where balancing research and action is hard under current budgets.

The **FIERCE Actions** showcase how actors and organizations envisage and implement democratic innovation by challenging invisible structural logics of exclusion, delegitimization, and subordination within hegemonic frameworks. They encouraged reflections on democratic innovation not as top-down modernization, but as a radical transformation that recognizes interconnected and unequal power relations based on gender, race, and other inequalities. The FIERCE Actions emphasize that shifting democracy from the margins demands specific support, time, and a redistribution of power. The collectives implementing these actions demonstrated their ability to create innovative, solidarity-based efforts, while exposing structural tensions such as resource shortages, political challenges, and internal power struggles. The FIERCE Actions, thus, serve as vital spaces for experimenting with future democratic forms. They have led to tangible political learning outcomes: testing new organizational structures and strategies; creating alternative narratives; and experimenting with unlikely alliances. They demonstrated that feminist democratic innovation extends beyond the development of new

institutional mechanisms. It lies in the ability of collectives to reshape the political landscape from the margins, integrating criticism, care, imagination, self-determination, emotions, and engagement.

The FIERCE analysis of **eight case studies** (Denmark, France, Greece, Italy, Poland, Slovenia, Spain, Turkey) reveals that feminist movements exhibit five types of feminist democratic innovation: promoting women's rights and participation; creating subaltern counterpublics; enacting intersectional solidarity; engaging in feminist knowledge production; and developing hybrid activism. The latter includes feminist political practices that are notably hybrid in their communicative methods, target audiences, and mobilization techniques. It establishes intermediate spaces within feminist politics that transcend traditional dichotomies, such as the choice between autonomy and cooperation with the political system, or the contrast between rational argumentation and emotional and affective language. This represents a novel blend of feminist approaches that can reach and influence different publics.

Based on these findings, FIERCE presents four **key recommendations** for feminist research, activism, and practice: (1) Continuous attention to intersectionality and the (re)production of internal power dynamics in feminist democratic innovations; (2) Securing the resources needed to sustain feminist democratic innovations in time and space; (3) Active use of hybridity in rethinking and reenacting feminist activist practices; and (4) Critical reflection on the ambivalence of democratic innovation.

The FIERCE Project

In the three years of activity (2022-2025), the FIERCE project worked to provide theory and methods to revitalize alliances between the feminist movement, civil society, and political decision makers. This in times of growing social and economic inequalities, global conflicts and rising mobilizations of anti-gender actors. FIERCE pursued an interdisciplinary, multi-dimensional and multi-level framework, designed to move beyond the limits of narrow disciplinary approaches and nationally bound methodology. FIERCE also strived to gain a comprehensive overview and understanding of the feminist and anti-feminist/anti-gender movements, their practices and discourses, their impact on institutional arenas and political decision making, particular with focus on the period 2010-2021. FIERCE has covered eight case studies (Denmark, France, Greece, Italy, Poland, Slovenia, Spain, Turkey) representing a wide variety of contexts in terms of socio-political, geographical and welfare/gender regimes. Our approach has strived to provide a cross-cutting comparative analysis of the way in which gender debates and controversies have influenced five main gendered thematic areas: labour market; health and reproductive rights; LGBTQ+ rights; migration; and gender-based violence. Building on co-creation methods and on a strong alliance with civil society organisations, FIERCE conducted feminist labs and pilot actions to help reinvigorate democratic practices, in line with feminist inclusive and innovative visions for the future of democracy. FIERCE thereby sets out a bottom-up, problem-driven, and impact-oriented approach, bridging academic knowledge, policymaking, and bottom-up democratic strategies.

Introduction to Report on Cross-Country Analysis and on Emerging Democratic Innovations (D3.3)

In line with FIERCE's Work Package 3, *Cross-cutting comparison of thematic areas within a policy framework and feminist contributions to engendering democracy*, this deliverable (D3.3, *Report on Cross-Country Analysis and on Emerging Democratic Innovations*, in the Grant Agreement) examines feminist democratic innovations and their potential to revitalize democratic processes, foster alliance-building between actors such as activists, scholars, and political decision-makers, guide agenda-setting, and advance intersectional framings and approaches. The emphasis is on inclusive and democratic innovations emerging from FIERCE's research, particularly those developed through co-participative activities between researchers and feminist activists in WP4 (*Participatory research co-creation labs*) and WP5 (*Innovative strategies and solution pathways*), i.e., National Labs, transnational network and activities, and FIERCE Actions (see Grant Agreement, pp. 8-10). The deliverable also examines democratic deficits from a bottom-up perspective, proposing strategies and tools that feminist movements across Europe can use as inspiration to promote democratic alternatives and build intersectional alliances. We identify distinct types of feminist democratic innovations and present them as possible new pathways, while also critically assessing their capacity to renew democratic processes and the risks of reproducing exclusion and power imbalances.

The deliverable builds on various resources and empirical data generated during FIERCE's three years of activity (September 2022 - August 2025). It draws on results and observations gathered in the co-creation processes of WP4, which include the FIERCE Labs and the FIERCE Actions. Both involved bottom-up democratic processes of co-participation and co-creation at national and transnational levels. Additionally, the deliverable builds on interviews and activities conducted in relation to WP2 on feminist movements and democracies, using a methodological triangulation that combines interviews with politicians, civil society actors, and activists, alongside critical frame analysis (CFA) of selected social movements' campaigns and parliamentary debates. Drawing on the results from this work, as presented in the report of fieldwork results, D2.2, all FIERCE partners have contributed to a collaborative exchange by providing analyses of feminist strategies and tools for more inclusive and democratic decision-making in the eight country cases as well as at a trans-European level. This process led to the elaboration of nine internal case studies reports that have served as input for this deliverable.

The deliverable also relates to D3.2 in WP3, which conducts a multidimensional and multilevel comparative analysis of key thematic areas across the country cases, with a particular focus on policy impact and policy processes. While D3.2 covers both anti-feminist/anti-gender and feminist mobilizations, providing novel insights into the contentious dynamic between these competing

movements, the present document (D3.3) focuses primarily on feminist movements and their democratic practices.

One of the major tasks here is the conceptualization and identification of what we refer to as democratic innovations, particularly when applied to feminist movements. This is challenging, as it requires engaging with the meaning and practices of innovation in promoting democracy, while doing so critically and responsibly by recognizing strengths and highlighting limitations in advancing feminist and democratic ideals. We determined that a suitable starting point was to first critically examine understandings of innovation in relation to democratic practices in scholarly work, based on the theoretical assumption that there is no ideal type of democracy which we can assume as an already established standard. Instead, we argue that democracy evolves through multiple forms and is inherently shaped by inequalities and conflicts (Lefort, 1986). Although democracy may be the most self-reflexive form of political practice, it also involves continual engagement with its own limits and the conflictual aspects of politics. Furthermore, democracy cannot be contained within the boundaries of the nation-state but operates in multi-layered, multi-scalar settings, developing through political configurations ranging from local to global. We explore the meaning of democracy within the context of innovative feminist practices in the first chapter of the deliverable. It is worth noting that in addressing the multi-layered nature of democratic practices, we also seek to balance consideration of differences in country contexts with a thematic, cross-cutting analysis at the trans-European level.

Overall, D3.3 is divided into five chapters. Chapter 1 provides a literature review and critical state of the art on democratic innovations and feminist practices. Chapter 2 offers a general introduction to the co-creation processes in the FIERCE project, which also constituted our main sources of analysis and discussion of feminist democratic innovations. Chapter 3 analyses specific characteristics of the FIERCE Actions, which were funded and implemented with the specific purpose of promoting feminist achievements and democratic innovation. Chapter 4 outlines the findings from the FIERCE country cases (Denmark, France, Greece, Italy, Poland, Slovenia, Spain, Turkey) as well as the European level and presents and discusses the major types of feminist democratic innovations that are recurring in the different contexts. Finally, we wrap up the deliverable with a critical discussion of our findings in chapter 5, outlining key factors in consideration of the existing literature and providing concluding reflections on which democratic strategies and tools are recommendable for feminist movements today.

1. Democratic Innovations: A Critical Literature Overview

Democratic innovation has attracted growing scholarly attention in recent years, partly as a response to the crisis and drawbacks facing many democratic societies. These challenges have spurred interest in approaches that help revitalize democracies in distress (Jacquet et al., 2024). Research has focused not only on democratic challenges but also on debates about democratic participation and citizens' role and engagement in fostering new forms of deliberation and decision-making. Citizens' participation and its impact on democratic institutions and policymaking have long been subject of scholarly discussions. Already in the late 1960s, Arnstein (1969) developed a typology illustrating eight levels of citizen participation represented as a ladder pattern, where each rung reflects a level of citizen power over (democratic) outcome. Arnstein argued that citizen participation is valuable if it involves "the redistribution of power" that enables the "have-not" citizens to be deliberately included in shaping the future (1969: 2016). Arnstein's 'Ladder of Citizen Participation' can be used to frame democratic innovation by showing how new democratic practices shift participation upward on the ladder, from tokenistic or symbolic engagement toward genuine power-sharing. Accordingly, the lower rungs represent illusory involvement, such as manipulation, whereas the upper rungs stand for highly empowered participation, including partnership, delegated power, and direct citizen control. The middle rungs are characterized by tokenism, covering informing, consultation, and placation. Arnstein's framework can still be used to frame forms of democratic innovation by showing how genuine innovative democratic practices ought to lift citizen participation upward on the ladder.

In this context, the term "democratic innovation" has become an overarching label referring to a range of different democratic practices, though the use of the concept is often criticised for its lack of clarity and imprecise boundaries, which can turn it into a buzzword that risks losing its analytical significance (Elstub & Escobar, 2019). Yet, the notion of democratic innovation still helps to challenge the idea of a stable form of institutionalized democracy, while also prompting reflection on the idea of democracy itself and of its boundaries. Ongoing debates and diverging traditions within democratic theory question, in fact, the idea of a stable form of democracy (see e.g. Mouffe, 1992). Particularly, the two faces of democracy, the "idealistic" or "redemptive" and the "pragmatic" have been highlighted to flesh out the inherent tension of representative democracy (Canovan, 1999). While the ideal/redemptive form is conceived as being powered by the people, the "pragmatic" one refers to the institutional, rule-based and procedural democratic form (Ibid.: p. 2-3). Tension arises because redemptive democracy promises 'salvation' through direct rule 'by and for the people', whereas pragmatic democracy prioritises stability and functionality. Some scholars view this conflict as both persistent and essential to how democracy operates, evolves and improves (Gregersen, 2021; Mummery, 2016; Norval, 2009).

Whether democracy as such is to be conceived as a 'way of doing politics' that itself implies continuous re-negotiation and innovation to endure, or whether it is to be understood as a more stable form of

governance that innovation practices strive to both preserve and develop, is still a matter of discussion. According to adherents to radical democracy theories (e.g. Lefort, 1986; Lummis, 2016), democracy itself does not have a stable form. It exists dialectically through its constant development and redefinition, particularly in terms of who holds power and who does not. This debate links to the underlying distinction that is often made between, on the one hand, the values or ideals that democracy refers to, such as equality and freedom, and, on the other hand, the system or practices that are meant to realize such values. According to some democratic theorists, there exists a constitutive gap between these two dimensions, entailing a persistent frustration among many that democracy in practice seems far from the ideal type (Bilakovics, 2012). In this context, democratic innovation – by its very nature – must trigger significant transformation as to what is seen as ‘politics as usual’ and the ‘status quo’.

Democratic innovation thus entails an intrinsic and strong element of democratic improvement, prefiguring a new condition/state of things that changes what goes wrong in the actual political situation, generally in relation to the persistence of power asymmetries and inequalities. In this sense, democratic innovations must be a constant, rather than exceptional, aim in democratic politics, since democracy per se is a constant struggle in striving to achieve equality and voice (Hirschman, 1970). The concrete political acts that can contribute to transforming the political systems may differ from context to context: from more traditional, organised and institutionally driven actions to movement, grassroots-led initiatives such as protests, boycotts, alternative media content production and through everyday individual interactions with the state. The scholarly literature on democratic innovation also emphasises the need to consider the impact of these actions regardless of whether they happen outside or within the political system (Jacquet et al., 2024). These theoretical insights, however, need to be operationalized and interpreted with emphasis on the historical, geographical, and political contexts, as well as on the envisaged and produced effects, to avoid generalizing innovativeness in absolute terms.

Using democratic innovation as a theoretical and interpretative device with a feminist critical perspective also sheds light on the normative and politically charged aspects engrained within the term “innovation”. Innovation is commonly portrayed as a self-evidently positive force — a symbol of progress, novelty, efficiency, and modernity. Yet, beneath this optimistic surface lies a terrain of contestation, negotiation, and ideological framing. Scholars have increasingly argued that innovation is not a neutral or apolitical process, but rather one imbued with power relations, serving particular interests while sidelining others (Godin, 2015; Fagerberg & Mowery, 2015). Thus, “innovation” functions as a political tool, a discursive strategy that legitimizes specific policies, governance approaches, and social visions, mostly within a neoliberal framework aligned with techno-scientific trends. Distributional consequences, inequalities and power relations are often marginalized within mainstream innovation discourses, which tend to be de-politicized and sanitized, as scholars from feminist science and technology studies (STS), feminist technoscience, and postcolonial studies have contributed to highlight

(Harding, 2008; Anderson, 2024). Within these critical streams of feminist literature, the concept of innovation has, in contrast, opened the space to criticize dominant narratives and generate alternative imageries of what it means to be democratically innovative. For example, rather than viewing innovation as inherently tied to growth, progress and technology, alternative perspectives emphasize situatedness and embodiment (Haraway, 1988) embedded in values such as social justice, care, reciprocity, and slowness (Puig de la Bellacasa, 2017). Others have strived to flesh out the tacit and affective labour (mostly performed by women and marginalized subjectivities) that sustain formal innovation practices as well as advocacy for transformative innovation policies (Wajcman, 2004; Schot & Steinmueller, 2018; Harding 2008).

In this sense, applying the innovation lens to democracy has the potential of re-balancing the normative blindness towards power, inequalities and subalternity and putting them back at the centre of the discourse. Yet, this happens with the risk of reproducing the positivistic and normative 'vector' embedded in current uses and understandings of democratic innovation. Being aware of this, FIERCE strived to engage critically with the concept of democratic innovation, recognising its intrinsic paradoxes, while exploring its potentials to generate alternative feminist practices and imageries of democracy. Furthermore, our focus has also primarily been on content and praxis rather than on perfecting the terminology.

The FIERCE approach to democratic innovations has its specific situatedness, since the project explicitly focused on the challenges to democracy derived from attacks on gender equality, considered a founding principle of democratic life. The latter is today challenged by anti-gender and anti-feminist actors, supported by broader anti-democratic/autocratic political actors and alliances (at times holding governing power). In this sense, the FIERCE approach to democratic innovation emphasised contextual factors since anti-gender attacks and challenges have taken different shapes and posed threats at different levels of social and political life. Reading and re-interpreting the multifaceted ways through which feminist movements (and their allies) have responded to the hardened circumstances through the lenses of democratic innovations is the main objective of this deliverable (D3.3), which further supports the project's overall findings, propositions, and action results published and discussed elsewhere (see e.g., D3.2; D4.2; D5.2; D5.3).

In this chapter, we outline the state of the art based on the extant literature and debates on democratic innovation. To this task, we endeavour an effort to integrate the (still limited) production on the topic grounded in the feminist literature, aiming to open up spaces for an emergent and critically oriented *feminist contribution* to the democratic innovation field of research.

1.1. Varieties of Democratic Innovations in the Current Debate

In times of democratic crises and disaffection with traditional forms of political participation and representation, a variety of democratic innovations are being tested (Smith, 2009). In particular, scholars emphasize how co-creation, together with other collaborative methodologies, can help increase political participation. This can become embedded in a variety of practices, often announced and implemented by governments, and acting as forms of so-called “invited spaces” (Fung, 2006). These spaces are thought of as arenas for joint deliberation, for the co-creation of solutions to governance problems (Bächtiger et al., 2018). Indeed, concepts such as ‘democratic innovation’, and ‘democratic reform’ have been acknowledged and discussed for being subject to extensive theoretical stretching to be able to encompass a greater variety of approaches, both in terms of institutions, processes (spanning right from “mini-publics” to citizens’ juries, to referenda, to participatory budgeting and decision-making) and agency (top-down, bottom-up). However, despite such variety, the starting point is oftentimes reformist, in the sense that the literature does not suggest any deeper or radical change to the status quo, while innovations are most often thought to expand and eventually adjust/correct the already existing liberal representative system of government (Elstub & Escobar, 2019, p. 18). Yet, others see this as an opportunity for more direct and more representative democratic systems that can configure, or prefigure, new forms of democratic governance based on the direct and more participative selection of political representatives through elections, and the selection among candidates based, for example, on a principle of sortition (Urbinati, 2006; Nippel, 2016; Sintomer, 2018). In this context, there are no established conventions, but in contrast a wide variety of approaches in different democracies today as to what role referenda ought to play in a political system where elected representatives otherwise hold power (Reilly, 2018; Matsusaka, 2020). In addition to this, referenda are frequently claimed as the main tool for achieving broader and more direct representation by different political organisations, and especially by the populist right (see Altman, 2011; Qvortrup, 2018; Urbinati, 2018).

As anticipated above, there is no widespread and agreed upon typology of policy-oriented democratic innovations. Based on a definition of democratic innovation that is limited to what is “new to a policy issue, policy role, or level of governance”, Elstub and Escobar present a broad and ‘classic’ frame of four clusters of contemporary democratic innovations: 1) Mini-publics; 2) Collaborative governance; 3) Participatory budgeting; and 4) Referenda and citizen initiatives (2019, p. 25-27). What is commendable for this study is that the typology builds on a scoping review of other typologies and lists of different democratic innovations, while it also elaborates an assessment of what these four clusters cover.

They encompass, in fact, a wide range of possible options for how democratic innovations may differ from each other concerning, for instance, various modes of participation, levels of governance, and stages in the policy process. *Mini-publics* can, for example, assume many forms but are distinguished by being composed of citizens selected through sortition and with a strong emphasis on deliberation practices. *Collaborative governance* is similar, but it is not necessarily public since it can also be

established in closed forums. Instead, what distinguishes collaborative governance is the co-creation between citizens and public authorities within various forms of partnerships for democracy. The third type, *participatory budgeting*, is specific and unique through its policy area, namely public expenditure, and the inclusion of citizens, either through self-selection or sortition, in the decision-making within, for instance, a local, municipal or regional setting. Finally, *referenda and citizen initiatives* are identified as a fourth cluster of democratic innovation, and perhaps the best known amongst them, being defined by voting as the mode of participation and the engagement of all those entitled, or a larger group of citizens who decide (by own initiative) to actively participate, particularly when it comes to issues of public concern and the wish to change them. These four clusters are, of course, not entirely distinct from each other and not entirely exhaustive of the range of possible democratic innovations. However, together they cover most of what has been studied in recent years, especially under the umbrella of *policy-oriented democratic innovations*.

Another stream of literature frames democratic innovations as encompassing new political practices in settings that are not, at least not directly, connected to a policy level or governance process. These studies position citizens' participation in a critical role, with the aim of countering/re-balancing existing power structures. This is, for instance, the case of agonistic approaches to democratic innovation, where the democratic project is not seen as a search for "shared solutions to shared problems", but rather as the process of turning enemies into adversaries who mutually recognise each other's legitimacy to inhabit the political space (Dean, 2018; Mouffe, 2005). The democratic innovation that follows this approach builds on both informal and institutionalised oppositions, in which citizens are not so much positioned as subjects to be consulted, or as collaborators, but rather in oppositional roles, as adversaries with agency who are inhabiting the same political space. For instance, Rosanvallon speaks of *counter-powers* (Rosanvallon, 2008) enacted by citizens who can agonistically exert 'prevention', 'oversight' and/or 'judgement', acting in different functions as both *veto-wielders* (for example through campaigning, protesting and other oppositional actions), *watchdogs* (surveilling/monitoring to prevent abuse or critically evaluating ongoing policies and denouncing their effects or lack of impact), and also *judges* (e.g., via assessments of governance actions).

The examples above emphasize the different foci, scopes, and conceptualisations of democratic innovation within scholarly literature. While the perspectives offer several theoretical insights, systematic empirical evidence on implementation and outcomes is still limited. This arguably leaves gaps in understanding how such democratic innovations are triggered and function in practice, and particularly whether they can be considered to produce the 'desired' transformative effect.

What is interesting to note, in particular for FIERCE given its focus on feminist movements, is that in most of the literature production on democratic innovation the role of social movements is not in scope, while innovation within formal political structures/institutional mechanisms remains central. However,

in recent years it has become more common to also conceptualize emerging social movements and their impact on politics as large-scale examples of democratic innovation. Like many scholars' positive views on policy-oriented democratic innovations, there is also optimism and hope expressed about the innovativeness of social movements. This clearly emerges, for instance, from Donatella della Porta's book title *How Social Movements Can Save Democracy: Democratic Innovations from Below*, published in 2020. Of course, social movements regularly influence and intervene at a policy level by, for instance, promoting referenda, influencing agenda-setting, or leading to the establishment of movement-parties that run for elections, or in other ways become directly engaged in the political system. However, social movements are essentially characterized by emanating from civil society as a dispersed space around the political system, which can be both private and public. As della Porta underlines, *democratically* driven social movements can also provide opportunities for experimentation with new modes of participation, deliberation, and decision-making outside an institutional setting (2020, p. 13-14). For some mobilizations such as Occupy Wall Street, the anti-austerity 15-M movement in Spain, and the pro-democracy movement in Hong Kong, this is coupled with a strong critique of the political system and current power holders. Such experimentation is therefore often perceived as a necessary exercise in the practice of *prefiguration*, understood in the sense of attempting to enact democratic ideals that one seeks to expand at some point onto a much larger political scale. As Cristina Flesher Fominaya puts it, such social movements are "laboratories of democratic experimentation in which shared critical and alternative understandings of democracy develop, as activists explore what "good" or "real" democracy might look like, and what is required for it to work" (2022, p. 85).

1.2. Studies on Feminist Democratic Innovations and Emerging Perspectives

There are no clearly defined limits for what counts as a strictly scholarly feminist approach to democratic innovation. Given that feminism is a historically evolving and diverse tradition of thought and practice, often involving fierce contestation between different feminist schools and movements, feminist democratic innovations are also historically embedded in such political and sometimes contingent developments. Analysing feminist democratic innovation at the municipal level, Caravantes and Lombardo (2024) defines the term as "feminist politics which contributes to democratising institutional politics in innovative ways to the extent that it reimagines citizens' role in governance and policy processes by proposing intersectionally inclusive and participatory policy and politics" (p. 178). It includes actions that transform knowledge, policymaking, public funding, institutions, and civil society coalitions. The aim of feminist democratic innovation is to challenge hierarchies and inequalities, and work towards achieving intersectional justice through new forms of citizen participation and inclusive deliberation, thereby deepening democracy (ibid.).

Overall, the current literature on feminist democratic innovations points to at least four types of such innovations, recalling the different streams of the literature highlighted in the paragraphs above and

encompassing both policy-oriented forms of democratic innovation as well as social movements (their impact and practices) as spaces of democratic innovation and experimentation. These four types are: 1) *The promotion of political equality* through, for instance, gender quotas for elections or empowerment programs for women (candidates, elected, or activists); 2) *The creation of subaltern counterpublics* that provide novel deliberative spaces of empowerment for women and other subordinated social groups; 3) *The emergence of intersectional approaches* to democratic processes, such as the inclusion of groups that are disempowered due to intersecting identity markers and the shaping of intersectional solidarity among feminist movements as well as cross-movements; and 4) *Feminist knowledge production* shaping new ways and mutual learning activities to, for instance, counter anti-gender attacks on democratic values and institutions. In the following paragraphs, these four types of feminist democratic innovation are elaborated in the order listed above.

1.2.1. The Promotion of Political Equality

Democracy, and politics in general, is historically a domain dominated by men. In this perspective, it is per se a democratic innovation to include women (and other marginalized groups) in democratic processes through, most noticeably, the struggle for women's suffrage, acquiring the right to vote, but also the right to stand for public office and to participate in public debates without being delegitimized for being a woman (Beckwith, 2021). As Andrea Cornwall and Anne Marie Goetz argue (2005, p. 783), the political inclusion of women can be conceived as a logical consequence of ascribing to democratic values, particularly the equal right to political participation for all citizens, resulting in what some call the "democratization of democracy itself" (Frateschi, 2016; Schubert, 2004; Sintomer, 2019).

In recent decades, this has been discussed in relation to the introduction of gender quotas for women, particularly in political party organisations and legislative assemblies. The use of electoral quota in the European Parliament (EP) elections varies across member states in terms of both legislated and voluntary quotas (European Parliament, 2023). In the party groups of the EP, some have established internal quotas to ensure balanced representation in their parliamentary work and decision-making (Kantola & Rolandsen Agustín, 2019). Globally, in countries such as Tanzania, Pakistan, and Bangladesh, seats are reserved in the national parliaments for political parties' own female nominees in proportion to the seats that they have won. However, it remains a subject of continuous debate whether the *descriptive representation* of women in politics, i.e. their actual presence in political bodies, also results in what is usually designated as *substantive representation*, i.e. the adoption of and support for new feminist policies (Lovenduski, 2005; Escobar-Lemmon & Taylor-Robinson, 2014). *Symbolic representation* also matters for women's political participation, especially in terms of the construction of specific gendered roles which influence who gains legitimacy and voice in the political space and discourse (Lombardo & Meier, 2014). Research and practice have emphasized the need for addressing parliaments more comprehensively as representative institutions that build on certain norms that may

favour gender equality, and women's participation in politics, or not, and that parliaments hold an obligation to develop gender-sensitive policies and practices to fulfil their role in society and democracy (Inter-Parliamentary Union, 2025; Palmieri, 2018).

Thus, there are several ways to innovatively advance the inclusion and empowerment of women in democratic processes, some of which relate directly to the policy level, such as gender quotas for elections, while others are more indirect, such as the empowerment of women's political voices in social movement activities, including online campaigns and creative street protests with this specific purpose, or within communities (Radsch & Khamis, 2013; Fornalé & Cristani, 2023).

1.2.2. Subaltern Counterpublics

As to the feminist democratic innovation involving the creation of counterpublics, Nancy Fraser's work on building so-called *subaltern counterpublics* provides an essential reference in developing a feminist approach to the public sphere (1990; 1996). Fraser criticizes Jürgen Habermas' famous conception of the public sphere as an idealized sphere, excluding both non-bourgeois and non-liberal publics. Oppression structures might be reproduced also in democratic innovations that follow such a universalist and liberal approach, for instance by subordinating the private and domestic spheres to the public one, or by delegitimizing relational-emotional arguments compared to rational ones (Martínez-Palacios, 2017). In this context, feminist counterpublics can be conceived as being parallel discursive arenas, where members of subaltern social groups produce and disseminate counter-discourses. These allow them to formulate antagonist interpretations of their identities, interests, and needs. Feminist counterpublics can, on the one hand, function as spaces of withdrawal and regrouping while, on the other hand, they can serve as preparatory sites for transformative activities directed to wider publics.

Based on a case study of women's experiences from different counterpublics within participatory budget experiments in the Basque country, Jone Martínez-Palacios identifies three major logics that are explicitly criticized, or challenged, through feminist counterpublics (2017):

- I. The logic by which private and particularly domestic matters are routinely delegitimized, or at least counted as less important than public issues and public engagement;
- II. The logic by which relational-emotional arguments are valued less and systematically ignored in public discourse, compared with so-called rational argumentation;
- III. The logic by which, with the scope of enlarging the public sphere, a universal model of participation, which ignores possibilities of other modes of participation, is imposed from above, for instance through the lack of a recognition of people's right to family life.

These three types of logics are challenged by feminist movements in their campaigns and within their organizations. Understandings of democratic innovation within these logics, risk limiting the transformative democratic potential and reproducing existing power relations (Asenbaum, 2022;

Machin, 2023). Discrimination against women, LGBTIQ+ communities, and other marginalised groups can remain overseen and reinforce inequalities in participatory democratic practices, with entrenched gender hierarchies persisting even within civic action spaces. Neglecting gender and patriarchal power structures in the initial political design and prefiguration phases of the innovative practice can undermine deliberative democracy and threaten the attempt to create and sustain inclusive participatory avenues. Rather than focusing solely on institutional mechanisms for citizen presence, some critics argue for the need of prioritising genuine bottom-up, citizen-led engagement and control over government in the first place. This entails greater attention from the beginning to cultural dimensions of deliberative democracy, namely, “the ethos, social norms, and self-understandings that shape and constrain political processes” (Böker, 2017).

Innovations in modes of participation and decision-making in social movements that ascribe to feminist principles and practices have a larger scope and level of ambition than setting up small-scale and perhaps also temporary mini-publics. For example, it has been noted how many social movements are innovative by making space for emotions and the use of body language, beyond discursive forms of expression. The development of different ways of expressing and building consensus is encouraged to move beyond vote-seeking practices and unanimity, which do not take into account power dynamics or underlying conflicts (see della Porta and Doerr, 2018). Social movements can function as “laboratories of democratic experimentation”, in which alternative imaginaries of democracy develop, while alternative practices of, for instance, decision-making processes are tested and evaluated (Fominaya, 2022, p. 85). In this sense, social movements can constitute platforms for a *prefigurative feminist politics*, facilitating future-oriented actions that may point the way forward in terms of how democracy can become engendered in new ways, while promoting gender equality.

1.2.3. Incorporation of Intersectional Approaches

Another central feature of feminist democratic innovations is their *incorporation of intersectional approaches*. In line with calls for increased citizen participation as motivation for introducing democratic innovations, intersectionality is often situated as a key factor in determining whether specific innovations are inclusive, and how one aspires toward more inclusion for disempowered groups. As Marta Wojciechowska (2019) points out, this does not simply mean including members of societal groups who are otherwise excluded as the result of the intersecting of two or more disempowered identity markers. It also implies the *aspiration to include* those who identify themselves on a more dynamic identity spectrum, without referring to stable and existing/recognized identity-categories and markers, like people with a non-binary gender (Wojciechowska, 2019, p. 2). In this sense, feminist democratic innovations ought to rely on both an *inter-categorical* approach focused on the interplay between categories and an *anti-categorical* approach that challenges the fixity of identity markers (McCall, 2005, p. 1773).

Feminist approaches to policy-oriented democratic innovation understood through the lens of empowerment engage with ideas about the relationship among actors, resources, and authority. Democratic innovation is often conceived as being sparked by those who already hold political or economic power, and act as elected representatives in political institutions or organizations. This approach implicitly reflects goal-driven and institutional procedures, where forms of empowerment and representation are mainly interpreted within the frame of 'power over' or 'power to', which are hierarchically projected and enacted forms of empowerment from top-down. Feminist scholars strive to challenge this with a multi-level, relational view of power. Allen (1999) distinguishes between power over (constraining choices of another actor), power to (ability to attain an end, despite subordination) and power with (group acting together to attain an end). The conceptualization implies a differentiation between the relational dimension of power over, the individual dimension of power to, and the collective dimension of power with. By emphasizing power-from-within (self-confidence, agency) and power-with (collective action), feminist literature conceives empowerment and innovation as an open-ended process through which it is possible to redefine choices, challenge structures, and build solidarity.

This reorientation also tackles the public-private divide that often limits conventional politics to formal institutions. Within this frame, Celis and Childs (2020) developed a feminist institutional design for parliaments, introducing the category of *affected representatives of women*, which represents the diversity of women as part of civil society. In such an institutional design, the affected/targeted representatives of women co-exist and collaborate with the elected representatives of women at the level of decision-making, focusing on advocacy and accountability. This is done to ensure that the interests of diverse groups of women are actively shaped and included in the policymaking process. Affected representatives are expected to be active not only at the advocacy level, articulating propositions from various women's groups. Structured rules should also guarantee that the affected representatives can assess and shape the outcome of the political process. Accordingly, representation and empowerment become a dialogic and interactive relationship within the electoral institutions throughout the policymaking process. Research also emphasizes that inclusive, intersectional policymaking requires explicitly addressing relevant inequality categories in policies, while articulating the intersectional relation between them, ideally building on transformative and structural understandings. In addition to regular consultation of civil society actors, this demands awareness of power logics and dynamics, privileges, and attention to the risk of stigmatization of specific minority groups (Lombardo & Rolandsen Agustín, 2012).

In addressing democratic innovation from the perspective of social movements and their experimentation, feminist studies stand out for highlighting innovative forms of cross-movement coalitions inspired by intersectionality theory, often without making explicit use of the term 'democratic innovation', but still pointing out the novelty of the approaches, seldom appraised by other scholarship

contributions. An instance of this is the work of Rossella Ciccia and Conny Roggeband (2021) who studied the democratically innovative coalition work developed around reproductive justice and domestic workers' rights in the US and Europe (2021). Their results point to a persistent problem of unequal power hierarchies in *intersectional alliances* between civil society organizations, but also the potential for transformative solidarity through efforts that counteract such power hierarchies and through the active recognition of differences. As the two scholars write with emphasis on the challenges of intersectionality: "(...) intersectional solidarity involves constant work by organisations to address power disparities at the symbolic level of how issues are framed, and an equally deep transformation of the material structures through which power works within coalitions" (2021, p. 187). Similarly, in her analysis of France and Canada, Lépinard (2014) argues that women's rights organizations use intersectional solidarity and intersectional recognition as part of their repertoires of inclusive practices. Intersectional recognition refers here to minority women's self-organisation (representing their own needs and interests), whereas intersectional solidarity is defined as the inclusion of minority women through representation and agenda-setting in single-axis organisations.

1.2.4. Feminist Knowledge Production

Literature on *feminist knowledge production* addresses the epistemic power dynamics leveraged, e.g., by anti-gender and anti-democratic political forces in their attempts to de-legitimize gender studies and feminist politics. The main strategy of these forces is to frame gender and feminist studies as ideological, unscientific, and not evidence based. Lombardo, Kantola and Rubio Marin (2021) stress the central role of feminist politics as a key democratizing force, and Paternotte and Verloo (2021) show how knowledge is interwoven with polity and plays a crucial role in the construction of democratic, or illiberal projects of society. They argue that politics of knowledge has become central to the current wave of de-democratization in Europe (see also Segers, 2025; Krizsán et al., 2025; Băluță & Băluță, 2025). Attacks on academic institutions and gender studies by far-right populist actors (see also D2.2) and increasingly authoritarian regimes exemplify the symbolic and material 'cultural warfare' promoting new politics of truth. In a thwarted appropriation of the Gramscian concept of "cultural hegemony", gender studies are regularly accused of being ideologized, while alternative truths and knowledge made compatible and functional to the illiberal political project are promoted and funded.

This shows how shaping and thinking of feminist pathways to strengthen and innovate democracy cannot leave aside feminist knowledge production practices. Innovation in this domain points at the need for critically rethinking power relations and alliances between feminist scholars, experts/academics, and decision-makers who explicitly and actively support feminism and feminists. In this context, feminist knowledge production and sharing often involve a mutual exchange between scholars and various feminist actors, ranging from grassroots activists to professional NGOs and politicians, instead of an unequal top-down process. Thus, feminist knowledge production as a more

horizontal epistemic practice contains an element of prefigurative politics in the sense of enacting principles of equality and solidarity across society that feminist movements continuously work for.

Overall, across the four types of emerging feminist democratic innovations elaborated above, current studies repeatedly underline how feminist movements are reconfiguring and experimenting with democratic practices, reimagining contemporary models of democracy, while at the same time pointing to the challenges faced by both internal power inequalities and external pressure from political systems and anti-feminist movements.

In terms of feminist democratic innovation, the focus of the FIERCE project is on the practices of feminist movements in their construction of counterpublics as well as co-creation as feminist knowledge production involving a variety of feminist actors. Of particular interest here is the notion of hybridity in the relations between politics, activism, and research, challenging established dichotomies and transforming ways of interacting. This also means that the FIERCE analysis pays less attention to more mainstream understandings of democratic innovations translating for instance into gender representation, participation and electoral rules (e.g. quotas, parties' gender composition, etc.). The FIERCE focus is on civil society and social movement experimenting and practicing intersectionality, solidarity, power dynamics, and emotions as part of feminist democratic innovation.

2. The FIERCE Labs: Co-creation as Democratic Innovation

Co-creation is one of the features of democratic innovation related to innovating governance models (Ansell & Torfing, 2021) and a practice increasingly integrated in research projects (Vandael et al., 2018). In FIERCE, we have chosen to hybridize some of the theoretical models related to co-creation with a feminist perspective and intersectionality as part of our overall PAR (participatory action research) approach.

At the core of our co-creation with feminist movements, actors, and allies, we have employed the FIERCE Labs. The Labs were implemented within WP4 and organised at both national and transnational levels. All FIERCE partners (seven academic partners and two NGOs) took the responsibility to set up, coordinate, and run feminist Labs in each country. The coordination of the overall activities happened under the methodological guidance of the WP4 leader (Smart Venice srl, a consultancy specialized in gender equality policies and participatory processes). The Labs were conceived as “action-oriented dialogue processes” between feminist academics/experts and feminist movements and their allies (from institutions, organisations, and other movements). The action orientation consisted of setting the objective of achieving a co-created action/political outcome as a result of the Labs processes, to be implemented via dedicated project resources, so to deliver a set of “FIERCE Actions” promoting feminist democratic innovations. This set of FIERCE Actions was considered to complement the other, entirely grassroots generated Actions resulting from an open call targeting feminist movements and NGOs. The Actions generated within the FIERCE Labs are presented and analysed in this chapter, while the FIERCE Actions entirely implemented by feminist movements selected from the open call are the subject of Chapter 3. The former represented the FIERCE model of co-creative Labs, which can be characterized as hybrid invited spaces – a specific type of democratic innovation (see pp. 12) applied to a research and innovation project. The invitation to the co-creative and deliberative space was launched by the FIERCE consortium partners (i.e., institutional actors) addressing feminist movements, organisations, and NGOs. However, the boundaries between the participants were blurred since several of the FIERCE academics also position themselves as feminists and/or activists, while the invited feminist activists in several cases also have an academic profile.

The Labs aimed at providing a democratically innovative framework for feminist movements to strengthen their networks and repertoire of action with focus on different topics and, in some cases, craft creative responses to the challenges and attacks from anti-gender political actors. Claiming back academic knowledge production as rooted in socio-political positionalities, and activism as a practice that can stand in dialogue with institutional actors -even within fluid and temporary spaces- were important features of the feminist co-creative methodology enacted within the FIERCE Labs. Knowledge production throughout the Labs was a collective process that drew on the practical knowledge of feminist activists and on the insights of academics and activists. Thus, dialogue and collaborative

political action were facilitated between academia and feminist activism, striving to generate, in the process, innovative imageries for a feminist politics of knowledge (Paternotte & Verloo, 2021).

Methodologically and in the design and implementation of the FIERCE Labs (as well as in the subsequent analysis of the overall process and results), attention was paid to address the universalizing logics prevailing in (innovative) democratic practices that are criticized by feminist subaltern counter-publics and scholars (Martínez-Palacios, 2017; see also Chapter 1). This entails avoiding the subordination of the domestic and private to the “public”; recognizing relational and emotional arguments alongside rational ones; and resisting to impose universal models of participation, which would leave limited space for alternative possibilities. These approaches were operationalized in the Labs methodology (see D4.1) and in particular in the choice of facilitation techniques, making space for different forms of expression and group work dynamics interconnecting private/personal/political dimensions and fostering flexibility and different approaches for shaping and convening the Labs in the different country contexts.

Promoting transformative and intersectional solidarity (Ciccia & Roggeband, 2021) was also one of the main objectives of the Labs in terms of feminist democratic innovation. This entailed paying attention to how differences within and between organisations and subjects were reflected in the framing of issues. The design and implementation of the action-oriented dialogues in the Labs explicitly aimed at recognizing structural interconnections between inequalities and going beyond “common denominator” approaches, which tend to dilute minority groups’ standpoints. Therefore, partners have put efforts into fostering a “recognition of differences” instead and practicing coalition work by actively seeking to redress power disparities in resources and representation.

Each FIERCE Lab focused on a thematic area, co-decided either via a bottom-up process or proposed by a core mixed group of activists and the FIERCE partner in charge. Similarly, the process of inviting activists to join the Labs was adapted to each country context, and to the needs, constraints, and positionalities of the partners. This entailed an initial exploration of existing contacts and (political) relations with movements, networks, and NGOs as well as the use of an informal snow-balling approach to reach out to relevant actors. The FIERCE project and the Labs were also featured by an intersectional approach from the beginning, trying to include as many activists from minority groups as possible. In most of the co-creation Labs, an initial “core group” of activists accepted to be part of the process of formation of the Labs and to co-decide on the relevant theme(s) of discussion with the partners, to then proceed with identifying other potentially interested groups and collectives and to explore their interests in participating. Extending the invite to feminist bureaucrats or elected representatives within local or national governing/democratic bodies, which the feminist movements could identify as allies, was left open to decide upon by the Labs, based on the different political landscapes.

The co-creation process included three Lab meetings in person (one-day sessions) over a time span from September 2023 to July 2024, designed in different formats and adapting a blueprint and methodology prepared within the framework of the FIERCE project and drawing on feminist participatory pedagogies and facilitation methods (see D4.1). In general, the participatory dynamic entailed: 1) ice-breaking and ‘getting to know each other’ activities; 2) debating and sharing analyses of existing challenges for feminist movements and discussing political strategies; 3) deliberating on the political situation or policy-oriented actions to be implemented as the Lab’s main outcome to counter the anti-gender backlash; 4) organising a series of creative workshops on crafting the contents of the chosen political outcome; and 5) follow-up/next steps sessions. In some cases, an entirely bottom-up process was followed, closer to movement-led assembly forms, with the FIERCE partners as “observers”, while in other cases either the academic partners or the core group of activists had a more prominent role in organizing and facilitating the sessions.

Overall, each of the three National and Transnational Lab sessions engaged between 130-150 activists, and diverse (dis)continuity patterns in participation emerged, marked by reported challenges in time/resources availability as well as the capacities of the engaged collectives.

The co-creation process strived to follow transparency and accountability guidelines as an integral part of its methodology. This included communication with activists and participants so that after each workshop, instant minutes and next steps’ reports (written in the respective national languages) were prepared by the FIERCE partner in charge and shared with the Labs’ members. Periodically, and according to the WP4 timeline, the partners submitted analytical reports of the workshops, summarizing discussions on specific contents, describing the dynamics and decisions taken based on a common template made available as part of the methodological guidelines prepared to support the process. A feedback questionnaire was sent to the 143 participants at the end of the whole process, leading to the collection of 50 answers (35 pct.) with uneven response rates across the Labs, the highest response rates achieved by the Slovenian, French, Italian, and the Transnational Labs. Most of the respondents reported high appreciation levels of the experience within the Labs, along with highlighting constructive critical reflections on aspects that could be improved. The analytical report drafted by the partners, together with the results of the survey, aimed at exploring key components of the theoretical framework that informed the FIERCE approach to co-creation, therefore focusing on perceptions from organizers and participants on:

- Internal decision-making and power dynamics;
- Participatory and deliberative practices in use;
- Agonistic and critical components of the Labs in terms of contents and political approaches vs collaboration with institutional politics;
- Space made for emotions;

- Intersectional alliances and solidarity.

A first analysis of the Labs, including the survey responses, is presented in earlier FIERCE deliverables (D4.1 v.1, v.2, and v.3) on co-creation methodology and dialogue session reports. These documents, together with additional reports from each partner on feminist democratic innovations emerging from the different research streams across WP2-4, including the Labs co-creation processes and the actions, provide the empirical basis for the reflections developed in the following paragraph.

2.1. The FIERCE Labs under the Magnifying Lens of Feminist Democratic Innovation

In this section, we delve into the main results of the overall co-creative processes, to critically reflect on these as instances of feminist democratic innovations.

At the national level, three of the FIERCE Labs focused on Gender Based Violence (GBV) and the anti-gender backlash (France, Greece, Turkey). The other themes addressed by the Labs were: reproductive rights and abortion (Slovenia), labour rights (Poland), sexual education in schools (Italy), care and care work (Spain), and sexism and intersectionality (Denmark). The Transnational Lab concentrated explicitly on the anti-gender backlash as a cross-cutting theme.

The Labs generated diverse types of outcomes. Three of the outcomes resulted in communication campaigns to enhance and spur public attention, in general or vis-a-vis a specific target group; this was the case for the Danish, Polish, and the Transnational Labs. In the French and Spanish cases, the Labs implemented the building of a network. The Turkish Lab's main outcome resulted in a policy brief, articulating the problems that Turkish civil society associations experience in their relations with Europe-wide international institutions. In the Italian case, the National Lab developed a 'self-defence' manual to equip teachers and activists with arguments and tools on how to defend education to differences/sexual education from anti-gender attacks in schools. The Slovenian Lab worked on a public exhibition on feminist claims and achievements on reproductive/abortion rights, the latter also in view of the 50th anniversary since the legal adoption. The Greek Lab's output consisted of the organization of three events in small to medium cities across Greece (Karditsa, Volos, Rethymno) where the insights from the Labs were disseminated and discussed with interested activists, scholars, and citizens, broadening the network and mutual learning from the Labs. Each session addressed locally grounded themes.

The Labs' themes and outcomes were influenced by context and reflected in most cases the most pressing challenges of contemporary feminist struggles and the configuration and arguments used by the anti-gender and far right in each country. In some cases, the Labs' innovative component consisted in the selection of an under-addressed issue such as the interrelation between sexism and ableism (Danish Lab), or the focus on labour rights from the perspective of care work (Polish Lab). The other

National Labs covered broader themes but with a re-framing approach such as the accountability of international organizations towards civil society (Turkish Lab); the intersectional and inter-territorial feminist approach to care (Spanish Lab); or the violence employed within reproductive health institutions that is often silenced when discussing sexual and reproductive health and rights (Slovenian Lab). Table 2.1 below shows an overview of the main themes and outcomes characterizing the FIERCE National and Transnational Labs, anticipating the types of feminist democratic innovations that the FIERCE partners have found to be emerging from the Labs' outcomes, with reference to the typology of four main feminist democratic innovations outlined in Chapter 1.

Country, main coordinator	Main theme	Title	Summary	Main type(s) of feminist democratic innovation
DENMARK Everyday Sexism Project Denmark	Fighting discrimination and sexism in marginalized groups	Intersectional Bystander Workshop and Game at the Youth Democracy Festival 2024	A dialogue card-game and workshop combatting intersectional sexism, where young people learn how to become active 'bystanders' to fight discrimination and sexism against marginalized groups.	Subaltern counterpublic Incorporation of intersectional approaches Feminist knowledge production
FRANCE European Alternatives	Fighting anti-Gender mobilisations	Online Resources on How to fight Anti-Gender and Festival	A platform gathering documents and tools produced by feminists NGOs on how to fight anti-gender and a feminist public event on fighting anti-gender. A Festival coordinated by the National Lab, with roundtables.	Feminist knowledge production Subaltern counterpublic Incorporation of intersectional approaches
GREECE Aristotle University	GBV, Fighting anti-Gender, legislative backlash and anti-sexist movements, feminist networks and the fight against GBV, and the emergence of LGBTQI+ movements	FIERCE Lab. The outcome in this case was the Lab itself and its entirely horizontal assembly format, where activists did not find it useful to engage in co-creating a specific outcome/action	A series of roundtables in Karditsa, Volos, Rethymno, bringing together researchers, activists, and feminist associations to share research findings on anti-gender movements. Based on a collaborative and horizontal methodology.	Feminist knowledge production Subaltern counter public
ITALY Smart Venice, SNS, Chayn Italy	Education to differences in schools	"Education of a different genre/gender". Self-defence manual for teachers	Self-defense manual for teachers in schools who actively promoted education to differences and sex education, providing a set of practical strategies to improve their response capacity when facing obstacles and situations of violence, notably anti-gender discourse, in their day-to-day activities.	Feminist knowledge production Subaltern counterpublic

POLAND University of Gdańsk	Labour rights	Women's labour rights	The campaign on 'women's labour rights' provided information on the gender-specific labour rights and the ways to secure them, covering ways to combat 'softer' forms of gender-based discrimination in the workplace.	Feminist knowledge production
SLOVENIA Mirovni Institute	Reproductive rights	Reproductive rights: On health, sexuality and equality of women	A feminist exhibition presented the key milestones in the history of reproductive rights in Slovenia regarding contraception, abortion, sexual education, artificial insemination and parenting rights, and violence in reproductive health.	Feminist knowledge production Subaltern counterpublic
SPAIN University Complutense Madrid	Care/reproductive work	An informal activist network of care	The initial deliberation's outcome of creating a formal network of movements/NGO was scaled down due to arising scepticism on the expected considerable effort required and past negative experiences. The mutual learning happening in the Lab with an intersectional perspective, a shared diagnosis of the care crisis in Spain, the political claims emerging, and the informal network generated are still considered as valuable outcomes.	Feminist knowledge production Incorporation of intersectional approaches Subaltern counter public
TURKEY Koç University	Feminism and Democracy	Feminist Co-creation: strengthening voice and increasing visibility	Production of a policy brief reviews existing participatory democracy processes utilizing an activist lens in combination with scholarly knowledge. It includes the production of a mini-documentary about the current state of democracy and the feminist movement and their imaginations about the future of both.	Incorporation of Intersectional approaches Political Equality Subaltern counterpublic
Transnational Smart Venice, EA, VILABS	Multiple themes	"Five FIERCE claims for a Feminist Europe" Campaign for the 2024 European Parliament Election	Design and implementation of the FIERCE Manifesto targeting candidates to the EP as an advocacy tool for an intersectional political agenda	Feminist knowledge production Political Equality Subaltern counterpublic

Table 2.1 Overview of the Outcomes/Actions Resulting from the Labs and Emerging Types of Democratic Innovations

The outcomes of the National Labs showed significant variation, ranging from concrete 'products' such as policy briefs, manuals, etc, to those less tangible, involving various types of communication and

engagement activities. The outcomes varied also with respect to the degree of resources that the participants could bring to the table and the timelines to which they were bound.

A closer look at the prevailing types of feminist democratic innovations as reflected in Table 2.1 shows how all the Labs' Actions were labelled as feminist knowledge production and subalterns counter-publics, four of them (Denmark, France, Spain, Turkey) as particularly successful in integrating intersectional approaches, while two other (Turkey and the Transnational Lab) in promoting forms of political equality. The prevalent form of democratic innovation was feminist knowledge production, which emerged from efforts to generate and share knowledge horizontally across diverse forms of activism and research. Feminist knowledge production was clearly at the core of the Labs' methodology as hybrid invited spaces and strongly shaped their outcomes.

In the case of Italy, feminist knowledge production focused on education and school system, central arenas of knowledge production and transfer, but also a key battleground for today's culture wars. Notably, ultraconservatives, anti-gender, and anti-feminists frame schools as strongholds against sexual education and diversity, considered ideological and harmful for children. In the Slovenian case, for instance, feminist knowledge production is understood as production of counternarratives. Curating the exhibition on reproductive rights, at times when these rights are under attack, emphasizes narratives of fundamental freedoms and bodily autonomy. This stands in clear opposition to the anti-gender narrative which frames reproductive rights as a threat to unborn children, women, and the Slovenian nation.

Subaltern counter-publics emerged across several Labs' Actions, particularly through challenges to universalizing and predominantly rational approaches to political engagement. This was evident, for instance, in the Danish context, where co-created videos against ableism and bodily normativity emphasized intimate and embodied perceptions, or in the French Lab's *Margins on Fire* Festival, where emotions triggered by performative arts were mobilized as driving forces of political conflict and collective action. The presence of subaltern counter-publics cuts across all Actions, opening space for critique as well as for transformative visions of democracy.

A defining feature of the Actions was their intersectional approach, reflected in the active participation of minoritized women's groups and the integration of struggles against sexism, classism, racism, homo- and transphobia into both content and strategic objectives. In Spain, this was evident in the focus on care and migrant domestic workers. In France, the *Margins on the Fire* Festival highlighted sexual and reproductive health and rights of racialized communities and transgender people, alongside resistance to state racism. The Actions' thematic breadth helped to expand the feminist framework of analysis, while creating connections between diverse social and political struggles.

The promotion of political equality as a form of feminist democratic innovation, directly targeting democratic institutions, was advanced by the Turkish FIERCE Lab Action and by the Transnational Lab. In the former, where democracy is threatened by an autocratic government, the Lab gave priority to the drafting of a policy brief, elaborating advocacy strategies and recommendations aimed at re-gaining space for feminist civil society in the institutional debate, by focusing on initiatives such as participatory monitoring of local level public policies, strategic litigation, and engagement with multilateral international organizations. Even if not explicitly marked as such in the partners' reports, political equality features in most Actions, for instance when efforts are put into including and empowering minoritarian subjects, by way of micro-organizational/logistic innovations (childcare availability, sign language translations, and the like). The Transnational FIERCE campaign targeting candidates to the 2024 European Parliament Elections, with its attempt to promote voices from feminist movements and make relevant scholarship heard within institutional politics, went beyond considering issues of political participation of women, focusing on the shaping of a feminist political agenda for the European Union. The five claims, presented in a manifesto for candidates to endorse as a non-binding commitment, included: recognizing a European feminist network to stop the antifeminist and anti-gender movement; social, economic and reproductive justice; fighting against SGBV (sexual and gender-based violence); protecting LGBTIQ+ persons' rights; and promoting global development, peace, and feminist foreign policy.

Finally, it is worth noting also how some of the Actions seem to "exceed" the types of feminist democratic innovations pre-identified in our literature review. For example, the attention paid to the spatial dimension of a mobilization, with the intention of regaining the public urban space for feminist topics (i.e., the outdoor installation of the Slovenian exhibition) and marginalized spaces, such as the French festival's deliberate choice to have events in working class banlieues. Also, the feminist digital activism characteristics of the Actions, such as the online campaigns in Denmark and Poland or the French online platform for activists, as a self-peer learning space to counter anti-gender/far-right discourses and politics stand out from our initial categorization of democratic innovations. The overlaps between categories and the emerging hybrid democratic innovations show that the "democratic innovation" approach functions more as an interpretative compass, rather than as a rigidly defined set of practices.

Few cases (Greece and Spain) where the National Labs did not result in a concrete outcome suggest that the adopted methodology did not always and necessarily support such achievement, either because of limited time or lack of sufficient resources which hindered the feasibility of the identified joint outcome. This opens up the longstanding issue of *implementation* when referring to democratic innovation (Jacquet, Ryan and van der Does 2025), which is subject to different considerations. For instance, it can spark discussions on "faster" and "slower" processes of (democratic) innovation (Puig de la Bellacasa,

2017), where the latter entails prioritizing mutual listening and learning over a “productivist” and delivery-oriented approach.

Despite such challenges, feedback from both partners and invited participants converge in conveying an impression of the Labs as *co-creative settings of academia-movements’ joint knowledge production, markedly appreciated for its emphasis on allowing movement knowledge to be central*. The Labs, overall, aimed at promoting gender equality and sustaining feminist political agendas in politically regressive times, guided by a shared effort to promote intersectionality.

2.1.1. The Labs Process: Hybrid Invited Spaces

The FIERCE Labs were conceived *hybrid* invited spaces, trying to pursue a democratically innovative process to foster horizontal dialogue between academia and activism, while challenging traditional hierarchies that privilege academic knowledge and expertise over mobilization practices and feminist activism as subjects of research, with the awareness and recognition of existing power relations and unbalances.

Both the FIERCE partners (in their reports) and the participants (in the survey) identified power dynamics and tensions. Significantly, one of the most highlighted features was generational differences, in certain cases explicitly referring to younger feminists’ feeling that they were struggling with being acknowledged by the older generation of activists and their defense of historical memory and struggles. Another cleavage showcased the horizontal styles of participation and debate between, on the one side, grassroots activists and, on the other, the more structured and formalised NGOs. Political disagreement was also raised as contentious on specific topics such as sex work and trans-inclusiveness, although in most cases the engagement process, building on and expanding existing contacts and alliances, and the Labs’ framing as explicitly intersectional helped minimize such conflict lines. Despite these tensions, the feedback received from Lab participants showed that they felt that their voices were heard and that FIERCE partners implemented adequate techniques, such as multiple rounds of discussion and other informal consensus-building methods, to ensure a balance of different standpoints and arguments, with voting being used only on rare occasions.

The Labs’ focus on co-created knowledge production to sustain political mobilizations benefited from: more strategic thinking; the co-creation of evidence to sustain feminist claims; and making space for sharing emotions, strengthening alliances, and nurturing the desire for joint actions, as it also emerged from the responses to the survey. Across the FIERCE Labs, emotions were marked by hope and resilience, alongside frustration and concern, reflecting the participants’ reactions to shared understandings of challenges and risks to democracy. A positive thread was the sense of hope and enthusiasm stemming from the formation of alliances, collective resilience, common activity, and the drive to counter anti-gender backlash.

Participants frequently expressed gratitude and excitement about being part of meaningful networks. This was for instance evident in the Danish case where feelings of indignation over persistent sexism were counterbalanced by happiness and appreciation for the National and Transnational Labs' role in fostering alliances and awareness. Similarly, in the Turkish Lab, participants highlighted their resilience during the first round of the Lab following the 2023 national elections, despite their dissatisfaction and frustration with the political situation. In other Labs, positive emotions emerged from a sense of collectiveness and community, for example in relation to the Greek and Slovenian Labs, where participants felt enthusiastic, connected and motivated by the Lab. In the Spanish Lab, hope and empathy emerged among participants from the dynamics triggered by the Lab's activities, alongside an acknowledgment of the left-wing political coalition as a window of opportunity. Yet, participants also voiced frustration and distrust regarding the broader political climate. In the Italian and French Labs, participants expressed positive feelings about the Labs but accompanied these with disappointment and concern about the constraints posed by the respective governments' conservative shifts and wider societal challenges, which were considered increasingly difficult to deal with at the national level.

Overall, the Labs and the variety of emotions that the discussions evoked reveal the need for further work on how to navigate the simultaneity of "negative" sentiments with "positive" ones in ways that do not avoid the former but make it a productive part of the discussion. In many of the Labs, the facilitators were able to do this by pre-emptively opening up the Labs with discussions of the issues and challenges that the participants faced. These discussions enabled the airing out of grievances while building a sense of community. The emotional dynamics underscored the Labs' role as spaces of both intersectional solidarity and collective action, even as participants navigated the challenging realities of rising right-wing and anti-gender mobilisations and politics in the respective countries.

2.1.2. The Labs Process: Democratizing Feminist Knowledge Production

With the aim of democratizing knowledge sharing and knowledge production, and avoiding knowledge extraction from movements, co-creation activities were designed to position the role of the FIERCE partners as facilitators rather than teachers or "knowledge transferers." Thus, space was made for activists to take active part (and the lead in some of the Labs or within certain phases) in discussions, deliberation, and the shaping of the political outcome-action that was expected as a result of the Labs, which in several cases was also a knowledge-based product (manuals, manifesto, awareness-raising campaign, etc.).

The FIERCE Labs aimed to establish a balanced power dynamic within the co-creation process, intentionally avoiding a participatory setting in which researchers acted as "extractors" of activists' knowledge and time. This balance was pursued through a progressive adaptation of the Lab methodology, informed both by the co-creation theoretical framework developed in WP4 and by insights gathered directly from activists during the engagement phase. As a result, the Labs were

designed as safe spaces, underpinned by a consciously and explicitly implemented intersectional approach. Thus, the results of the (knowledge) co-creation process put in place via the Labs has been successful in reflecting and adhering to feminist intersectional solidarity and pedagogy principles (see D4.1, Chapters 2.3 and 2.4, pp. 14-17).

To further mitigate the inherent power asymmetries linked to project resources, specific measures were adopted to counter extractive dynamics. Reimbursement for travel costs (and accommodation, where relevant) was ensured, and the time commitment requested from activists was deliberately limited as much as possible to attending three in-person sessions that represented the ‘value’ that the FIERCE project could make available to activists, for their potential to foster national and international networking and reciprocal knowledge exchange, while sustaining present and future political mobilizations. In addition, and consistent with this approach, the entirety of the organizational and logistic work was undertaken by the consortium partners. Furthermore, the allocated resources for the FIERCE Actions (see chapter 3), both those co-created from within the Labs and those that were made available at a later stage via an open call for actions to (co)fund grassroots initiatives in an entirely bottom-up way, were part of an overall effort to balance economic-power relations between the partners and the movements/NGOs engaged within the constraints and parameters of an EU funded research project. And yet, in some of the countries, it became clear that the limited economic resources made directly available to individual participants to support their participation were generating the impression, and more or less explicit criticism, of an unbalanced/extractive setting, particularly for those with economically vulnerable backgrounds. In this context, the consortium internally had to question the choices made at the project’s design stage of not foreseeing allowances to grant participants, i.e., in the form of expert fees, to compensate activists for their time. In general, this sheds light on more structural challenges of the funding programmes related to combining research and action-oriented components within EU funded Horizon RIA projects, whereas the “innovation” component is linked to on the ground and policy-oriented actions. It would be beneficial if the European funding bodies would take such challenges into account in the design and budgetary planning/mechanisms of Work Programmes, so to mitigate potentially extractive outcomes of stretching budgets between researchers and external networks of participants whose contributions are essential to the desired projects’ impact.

2.2. Challenges with Intersectional Inclusiveness

The most common profile of the FIERCE Lab participants, according to the Lab reports and survey responses, was a cisgender woman in her thirties or forties, with a higher level of education (Master’s or PhD), and a long biographical trajectory within the feminist movement. The Turkish and French Lab reports highlighted a lack of racial inclusiveness, as the main critique expressed by participants, in spite of the efforts made by the partners in charge of the Labs. The former emphasized the need to include Kurdish collectives, while the latter underlined the importance of involving collectives from the

migrant/racialized feminist movement in France. In the Turkish Lab, Kurdish activists based in Kurdish-majority cities had confirmed their participation in the first session but were unable to attend due to personal reasons. In the French Lab, a collective of Black feminists took part in an online preparatory meeting for the second Lab but later informed the organizers of their decision to discontinue their participation without providing an explanation. The FIERCE partner in charge assumed that the decision was linked to the lack of racial diversity in the core group of activists supporting the Lab. Also, the lack of funding associated with the requested time commitment potentially led to several racialised feminist groups refusing to join and attend the Lab.

The Spanish Lab stood out as the most diverse and intersectional in terms of participant profiles. According to its report, which profiled all 24 participants in the co-creation process, a quarter of them had a migratory background from Latin America. Additionally, one participant had a disability, and attendees came from a broad range of backgrounds, including activists, academics, politicians, and care workers.

Out of the 50 overall respondents to the feedback survey, 17 identified as LGBTIQ+, with representation across all Labs, with the exception of Slovenia. Eight respondents, across the Labs (except from the Slovenian and Greek Labs) identified as having an ethnic or migratory background, while eight respondents identified as having a chronic condition or disability, with no representation from the Greek, Polish, and Slovenian Labs. The challenge of having reproduced predominantly white ableist settings underscores how long and demanding the path toward truly embodying intersectional feminism in practice remains, requiring ongoing efforts, attention, and commitment from the initial and conceptual/design phases to guarantee intersectional representation. A further consideration, in retrospective, points at the potential positive effect of allocating additional resources since the project design/budgeting phase specifically intended to facilitate/support the participation in the Labs of activists with particularly vulnerable economic conditions (often intersected with other race/migrant background inequalities, in particular).

The integration of intersectionality into content development and the topics addressed in the Labs represent important steps forward, but it also highlights the need for more inclusive outreach strategies, deeper engagement with marginalized voices, and sustained reflection on power dynamics within feminist spaces.

Under the conceptual lens of democratic innovations highlighted in chapter 1, it is also interesting to look at the ways in which the FIERCE Labs navigated the movements/democratic institutions dichotomy. Most of the activists engaged in the Labs already had experience with forms of 'collaboration' with public democratic institutions/governance bodies through a variety of activities that can be broadly categorised as advocacy, service provision, policy development, capacity-building, and education. None

of the National Labs, however, opted for an action that would directly address formal structures of democratic representation, even if feminist claims and agendas/expectations in terms of policy changes were formulated across all Labs, and criticism against the political arena and the government in particular was often sharp, especially in countries with (far) right political parties in power. Interestingly, the Transnational Lab was the only Lab where the co-created outcome was a political campaign addressing candidates to the European Parliament. In a time when the democratic backlash is featuring more and more in national elections, the urgency and importance of contributing to safeguard European democracy has also become increasingly manifest in the FIERCE project and particularly in the activities and discussions within the Transnational Lab.

2.3. Concluding Remarks

In conclusion, the innovative dimension of the FIERCE Labs' efforts with co-creation lays less in the resulting forms of mobilisation and more in its development and knowledge-creation process as alliances between feminist academics and activists. These have been strengthened, with the aim of re-positioning the contribution of higher education and research to sustain democratic values in times where autocratic/antidemocratic forces are taking increasing power and space.

Reclaiming academic knowledge as rooted in socio-political positionalities and recognizing activism as a practice that can stand in dialogue with institutional actors, even in fluid and temporary spaces, were central features of the ongoing experimentation within the FIERCE co-creation Labs. This process required participants to inhabit uncomfortable spaces. Academic and institutional partners tackled the feelings of 'guilt' coming from holding relatively more power and resources. Activists dealt with feelings of suspicion and concern about their knowledge and experience being exploited for "academic use" and "intellectual extractivism." Navigating these hybrid spaces entailed a lot of context-sensitiveness not only from the FIERCE partners, but from all involved counterparts, starting from the engagement and the Labs' formation phase, throughout its implementation, driven by a strong belief in the possibility to shape meaningful feminist political action across boundaries.

At the same time, the experience has shed light on more structural tensions embedded in Horizon Europe funding frameworks, where the balance between research and action-oriented components is often difficult to achieve under current budgetary rules. Our findings suggest that EU Work Programmes could benefit from revisiting their design and financial mechanisms to account for the crucial contributions of external participants such as activists, and to prevent extractive dynamics in collaborative research. This would mean recognising co-creation not only as a methodological innovation, but also as a practice requiring dedicated resources that value time, knowledge, and labour fairly across different actors.

3. The FIERCE Actions as Democratic Innovation

This section analyses the concepts and practices of democratic innovation as formulated and tested by feminist organisations within the framework of the FIERCE Actions, based on the theoretical framework developed in the first part of the report (see Chapter 1). Eighteen FIERCE Actions were carried out at the end of 2024 and in early 2025 in the eight European countries of the FIERCE project. The actions were led by organisations, groups, and collectives engaged in the struggle for gender equality, women's rights, LGBTQIA+ rights and migrants' rights. Designed as 'political experiments' within a research-action framework, these initiatives did not only aim to illustrate alternative practices of citizen participation but also sought to question the status of contemporary democracy through, for instance, the critique of lack of inclusiveness, intersectionality, and deliberation.

The FIERCE Actions allowed for the concrete realization and observation of how the actors/organisations involved envisage, implement, and demand forms of democratic innovation by challenging the structural logics of exclusion, delegitimation, and subordination that are often invisible in (political) hegemonic institutional frameworks. The Actions encouraged reflections on democratic innovation not as a top-down process of institutional modernisation, but as a profound and radical transformation based on the recognition of intertwined and unequal power relations, rooted in gender, race, class, migration status, ethnicity etc., and on the legitimisation of situated forms (and habits) of participation, representation, and decision-making.

3.1. What Are the FIERCE Actions?

The FIERCE Actions responded to two different typologies: Actions from the National labs and Actions resulting from an open call to grassroots feminist organisations.

1) Actions from the National Labs

Seven actions were planned and co-created within the FIERCE National Labs (see Chapter 2) where the Labs acted as workspaces set-up by the FIERCE partners together with the relevant actors at national level. These collaborative workspaces brought together local and national feminist collectives, NGOs, feminist groups, artists, researchers and other relevant civil society actors around common themes. As detailed elsewhere (see D4.1) and in the chapter above, these laboratories were designed as hybrid, locally based, action-oriented mechanisms for identifying urgent issues in society for feminists and emerging from the democratic deficit and the mobilisations of anti-gender and anti-feminists. Each of the Labs identified problems, shared diagnoses, and jointly designed intervention projects. Some of these actions were closely supported by the project's academic and institutional partners, while maintaining a participatory approach in both design and implementation.

2) Actions resulting from an open call to grassroots feminist organisations

Eleven of the eighteen FIERCE Actions were selected following a call for applications aimed at financing grassroots organisations –local NGOs, informal collectives, associations, groups of artists, or activists–. The call aimed to involve and finance less institutionalised actors in the project and to promote autonomous ideas and forms of mobilisation, rooted in the specific realities of the territories affected by multiple conflicts and challenges to democracy.

The Actions proposed had to be politically, culturally, and/or artistically driven projects, falling within one of the five thematic areas of the FIERCE project –labour market, health and reproductive rights, LGBTQIA+ rights, migration, and gender-based violence– and implemented in one of the eight partner countries. The Actions also had to articulate an intersectional feminist approach with an explicit ambition to experiment with or expand forms of democratic participation.

The selection was based on several specific criteria: clarity of objectives, potential for democratic innovation, relevance of the democratic feminist approach, planned implementation methods, and expected outcomes. Particular attention was paid to the Actions' ability to:

- Combat anti-gender discourse and defend gender-related rights;
- Involve groups that are under-represented in the public sphere;
- Explore concrete forms of democratic participation;
- Create spaces for feminist dialogue (such as assemblies, discussion groups, or collective co-construction mechanisms).

While the selected Actions had to comply with this general framework, applicants were invited to define the objectives and formats of their Actions themselves, based on their strategic priorities and local context. This bottom-up dimension was a key principle of the call for proposals: the aim was not to propose a 'fixed' definition of and template for democratic innovation, but to allow the participants to formulate it themselves, based on their concrete practices in all their diversity.

In this section of the report, we focus on the FIERCE Actions resulting from the open call, since the outcomes in terms of innovation of the National Labs' Actions have already been analysed in Chapter 2. Focusing on the Actions supported by FIERCE but conceived and carried out entirely autonomously by the selected grassroots organizations, allows us to analyse the groups' or collectives' trajectories, their available resources, and their relationships with institutions influenced their forms of democratic experimentation — as well as their ability to claim strategic autonomy in often hostile environments.

The eleven FIERCE Actions ranged from public campaigns against Gender-Based Violence; feminist housing and kitchen projects; the creation of online platforms providing information on sexual and reproductive rights or countering anti-gender discourse; the production of comics or board games against LGBT-phobia; to cultural events combining various forms of intervention, from traditional roundtables to workshops, exhibitions, and artistic performances. While not all Actions resulted in

publicly disseminated deliverables, most generated significant results, such as capacity-building, political mobilisation, or network strengthening. In some cases, these results also took the form of concrete and shareable products, including training sessions, reports, advocacy, or awareness-raising tools. Table 3.1 below shows the list of the eleven FIERCE Actions resulting from the open call.

Country:	Organization name:	Main thematic	Title:	Summary:
Denmark	Center for Violence Prevention	GBV	Orange days in Aalborg	Events, including public stage (theatre) happenings, talks with organisations, distribution of informational goodie bags, and art exhibition. It included Support Groups and Workshops
France	Tant que je serai noire	Black women political representation and rights	Savoir Pouvoir: Réapproprions nos droits démocratiques	Empowering initiative designed to help Black women and gender minorities understand their democratic rights in France. Popular education model: workshops, interactive seminars, and accessible resources. Cultivate community leaders: Build a network of leaders who advocate for their communities and mobilize others to participate in democratic processes.
Greece	The boat collective	Migration	Musafir	3 days Workshop on re-memory, bodies, borders, to conceive a theatre play with migrants
Italy	Tourbillon ETS	GBV, Housing, Care	Arti femministe a Santa Chiara. Trasformare, sentire, formarsi	Role-play simulation on gender violence, Presentation of a self-organized community housing project, promoting sustainable, feminist urban spaces. Feminist kitchen, exploring care work and its intersections with gender, race, and labor conditions. The final objective is to realise a network of feminist practices to promote meetings and building of a feminist community that work on thinking of alternative ways of doing politics.
Poland	Fundacja Kocham Dębni	GBV LBTQI+ rights Migration (Ukraine)	gender debunking guerilla	Campaign - The campaign utilized stickers with QR codes, strategically placed in public spaces across Warsaw and Krakow, providing a simple and accessible way for people to obtain comprehensive knowledge about gender-related issues.
Poland	Fundacja Widzialne	Abortion	Akcja Aborcja	The action promoted access to safe abortion within the provincial and rural areas of Pomeranian region in cooperation with the Polish organization Abortion Dream Team, specifically via workshops on reproductive rights.
Slovenia	Transfeminist Initiative TransAkcija	LGBTQI and Trans-rights	LGBTIQ+ Radar	The action provided effective Response to Anti-Gender Narratives: Address and counter incidents of anti-LGBTIQ+ hate, such as discriminatory laws, media attacks, and violence at public events. Data collection on aggressions (in the media and physical aggressions) against LGBTQI+. It has created a Shared Database and Collaborative Platform, and created opportunities to raise public awareness and to build support. It contributed to solidifying the newly formed consortium of LGBTQI+ organizations and activists.
Spain	Mujeres Supervivientes	Fight Anti-Gender movements	Feminist Day; Theory and action in the face of Antifeminism	Round Table & Campaign on antifeminism in Spain
Spain	Parcela de Tierra	Intersectionality and Decoloniality	La Cenicera	Brasas project was a public event aiming at creating links between intersectional feminist, decolonial and queer organisations, as well as migrant and artistic organisations, in order to promote gender equality and combat the extreme right-wing discourse in Spain in the public space. It proposed a round table, a dinner and an artistic and cultural event, open to the different collectives and the general public.
Turkey	Women Worker Solidarity Association	Women Workers	Internal training and forum	Internal training for Kadınışçi reporters and volunteers on feminist methods and politics; Forum on the possibilities of feminist solidarity with workers' resistance.
Turkey	Kuir-Trans Feminist Karikatür Okulu	LBTQI+	Özgür Renkler LGBTI+ Derneği	A Queer-Trans Feminist Cartoon school was organised for 2 days. The workshops were organised in collaboration with queer-trans feminist illustrators, allowing LGBTI+'s to express their stories, experiences and social struggles in an artistic way.

Table 3.1 Overview of the FIERCE Actions Resulting from the Open Call

3.2. Democratic Innovations in the FIERCE Actions

The democratic innovation component of the Actions emerged from several sources and levels of analysis of the processes and outcomes, including:

- I) The Application documents, the observations and exchanges made during the Actions with researchers from the FIERCE consortium, who participated as observers, and followed the development of the FIERCE Actions in their countries.

- II) The documentation submitted by the FIERCE Action main coordinators (artistic, educational, advocacy materials, etc.)
- III) The responses to the survey submitted after completion of the FIERCE Action (specifically designed to highlight the dimensions of democratic innovation).

This data allowed for a qualitative analysis of the innovative component of the FIERCE Actions.

Going back to the analysis provided in Chapter 1, none of the FIERCE Actions emerging from the open call are directly connected to a policy level or governance process. Therefore, they come into the classifications mentioned in Chapter 1 more as counter-powers as defined by Rosanvallon, 2008. The FIERCE Actions were led in the framework of social movements and have come as laboratories of democratic experimentation, as Cristina Flesher Fominaya puts it.

The analysis will therefore follow the categories 2,3 and 4 of the typologies provided in Chapter 1:

- 1) The promotion of political equality through, for instance, gender quotas for elections or empowerment programs for women (candidates, elected, or activist);
- 2) The creation of subaltern counterpublics that provide novel deliberative spaces of empowerment for women and other subordinated social groups;
- 3) Incorporation of intersectional approaches to democratic processes, such as the inclusion of groups that are disempowered due to intersecting identity markers and the shaping of intersectional solidarity among feminist movements as well as cross-movements; and -
- 4) Feminist knowledge production shaping new ways and mutual learning activities to counter anti-gender attacks on democratic values and institutions.

3.2.1. The Creation of Subaltern Counterpublics

One of the major contributions of the FIERCE Actions to democratic innovation lies in the forms of governance they have experimented with. In this context, governance is understood as the decision-making, steering, and collective organisation mechanisms that structure intersectional feminist collectives. Although these initiatives clearly aim to disrupt dominant modes of political organisation, the degree of implementation remains scattered and substantially heterogeneous in the suggested forms, often limited to the local scale or to internal dynamics.

In more than half of the Actions analysed, the collectives sought to challenge vertical and hierarchical models of deliberation and experimented with horizontal and participatory/deliberative modes of decision-making, centred on relational and experiential knowledge. Rather than imposing decisions, these initiatives favoured systems in which negotiation, consensus, and active community participation played a central role. However, these modes often remained informal and limited, with uneven

formalisation and responsibilities, often resting on a small core of initiators. FIERCE Actions sought to reconfigure decision-making structures, to enforce truly collective decision making for instance — not merely expand participation. Nonetheless, in practice, several initiatives struggled to stabilise governance and articulate collective responsibilities, especially when constrained by time, or limited infrastructure.

Several collectives sought to build inclusive forms of governance, drawing on diversity : across social (migrants, racialised women, LGBTQIA+, precarious workers, survivors of violence), generational (young activists and experienced activists), statutory (volunteers, employees, informal or institutional members), professional (researchers, artists, trade unionists, social workers), and territorial diversity (rural areas or working-class neighbourhoods with limited access to support structures). This attention to the plurality of social positions and the recognition of differences is an essential lever for democratic reinvention. Yet, the FIERCE Action leaders reported difficulties in fully implementing the principle, notably when some individuals were more committed than others or had more time (as well as resources) than others. For instance, the initiators of the Musafir project, working with migrants, were confronted with the difficulty of some of the participants attending only some and not all of the sessions, therefore being less involved in the decision-making process around the project. These difficulties once again point to the need for more work on all kinds of participatory fora, with a focus not just on what they can produce, create, and achieve but also in which ways they can be taxing on the participants.

For many (pro-)feminist collectives, the inclusion of marginalised groups – migrant women, LGBTQIA+, precarious workers, young activists, survivors of violence – and the adoption of intersectional governance are ethical and political imperatives. These forms of governance are conceived not only as means, but often as ends in themselves. They seek to redistribute voice and decision-making power to the people concerned. Yet, the tension between these normative aims and the operational reality of the FIERCE Actions —limited availability, linguistic or legal barriers, reliance on unpaid labour— suggests that such redistribution remains a fragile and often contingent achievement, requiring constant adjustments and negotiation.

The *Savoir-Pouvoir* (“Knowledge-Power”) initiative in France, led by *Tant que je serai noire* (“As long as I am black”), illustrates this dynamic. By structuring political training courses designed by and for black women and gender minorities, the collective has not only produced emancipatory content but has also claimed a form of governance led by those concerned, without hierarchy, or external delegation. Still, this declared horizontality coexisted with an asymmetrical distribution of responsibilities, notably centred around the collective’s director, an aspect which we examine further below. The reconfiguration of governance contrasts with traditional forms of representation, which are often perceived as exclusionary, echoing theoretical debates on the crisis of representative democracy.

Nevertheless, the rejection of representative models does not always lead to clearly defined alternatives. In some cases, the absence of stabilised procedures, or mediation spaces, complicated the collective resolution of disagreements or recognition of differentiated contributions.

Other FIERCE Actions have focused on intersectional alliances and hybrid partnerships. For example, the action "Women's Rights at Work" (*Kadın İşçi*) in Turkey brought together trade unionists, activists, lawyers, and journalists. By highlighting the double exploitation suffered by women, both in the domestic sphere and on the labour market, this FIERCE Action directly challenged the unspoken gender biases of Turkish trade unionism, which often focuses on male and generalist demands for labour rights. By bringing together feminist, trade union and legal expertise, this initiative gave substance to a local democratic innovation, where the collective production of knowledge becomes a tool for reconfiguring public policy standards. FIERCE Actions contributed to the formation of genuine feminist counter-publics, for instance with the initiative *Savoir-Pouvoir* in France, whereby subaltern groups formulated their own interpretations of needs and rights, while experimenting with prefigurative political practices that embody the democratic models they work for. Yet these counter-publics are not immune to implicit hierarchies. While they create necessary spaces of autonomy and experimentation, they also reveal the complexity of sustaining inclusive governance over time, especially when structural constraints limit the redistribution of logistical and symbolic power.

3.2.2. Incorporation of Intersectional Approaches to Democratic Processes

The FIERCE Actions took shape based on the experiences of subaltern and marginalised groups, rather than according to pre-established models of action. However, the approaches did not refer to and bring forward a model fit for all. Rather, they reflected a multiplicity of situated trajectories, marked by experiences of discrimination, precariousness, and asymmetrical access to mobilisation resources — factors which have shaped both the scope and the form of the interventions.

The bottom-up approach, whereby priorities, strategies and alliances were defined by the groups themselves, can be seen as a form of democratic innovation. Yet, the degree of autonomy and co-construction achieved varied across Actions, depending on the actors' embeddedness in local networks, previous organizing experience, and room for manoeuvring. This is part of a feminist approach that criticizes power relations and deconstructs mechanisms of political dispossession (Lefort, 1986; della Porta, 2020).

The interventions are based on critical practices and theories such as popular education, narrative memory, body storytelling, and critical pedagogy (Freire, 2020, hooks, 2014), as well as situated knowledge (Haraway, 2016, Collins & Bilge, 2020). They have worked to put marginalized groups back at the heart of the definition of politics, redefining the terms of access to citizenship by valuing forms of knowledge that have historically been discredited. In some cases, this revaluation of marginalized

knowledge has clashed with dominant epistemic norms, including within progressive or institutional spaces, highlighting the persistence of cognitive hierarchies that condition what is recognized as legitimate political discourse.

This is what the Action "Arti femministe a Santa Chiara" (Italy), led by Tourbillon ETS, has implemented. By tackling gender-based violence, precariousness, gentrification, and marginalisation processes through the implementation of collective housing, a feminist kitchen, and trans-queer pedagogy, this initiative has turned everyday life into a space for self-management, care, and politicization. This type of intervention illustrates the notion of political prefiguration developed by Judith Butler (2015): here, democracy is not conceived as an abstract horizon, but as an immediate practice embodied in different forms of collective organization. Yet, the consolidation of such practices remains fragile when not supported by stable spaces of engagement, or long-term alliances. From another perspective, the "Survive the Borderlands" Action by *Boat Collective* and *Musafir* (Greece) has mobilized narrative and performative tools to restore visibility to the erased stories of migrants. Drawing inspiration from the works of Saidiya Hartman and Toni Morrison, this Action has reinvested inclusive collective memory as a resource to transform power relations and reconfigure democratic space.

Overall, these intervention strategies show that democratic innovation not only comes about through the creation of new institutional mechanisms, but also through a shift in the 'centre of gravity' in politics. By anchoring activism in the needs of communities and valuing knowledge gained from experience, the FIERCE Actions reconfigure the conditions of access to active citizenship. However, this reconfiguration remains constrained by the uneven recognition of these knowledges in public and institutional space, and by the limited resources available to ensure their dissemination and sustainability.

Inspired by the work of Kimberlé Crenshaw (1989) and Patricia Hill Collins (2000), most FIERCE Actions have incorporated intersectional analysis into the development of their strategies. By recognizing the intertwining of different forms of domination –whether related to gender, class, ethnicity or sexual orientation– these initiatives have sought to highlight the exclusions and blind spots of traditional democratic mechanisms. Yet, their ability to fully account for these complex entanglements has varied, depending on the political reflexivity and organizational tools available to each collective.

Some of the FIERCE Actions, such as the "Savoir-Pouvoir" project, focused on valuing knowledge and transforming the spaces in which it is transmitted by promoting popular education mechanisms that have been established as tools for emancipation and political transformation. By encouraging the production of knowledge rooted in community experience, they helped to reinvest the public space with alternative narratives and critical practices. However, the impact of these narratives outside activist, or community spaces has often been limited, especially in contexts where public debate is marked by polarization and hostility to feminist and anti-racist discourse. This raises the question of

how situated knowledge circulates and under what conditions it acquires political traction beyond its site of production.

3.2.3. Feminist Knowledge Production via New Forms of Political Action and Building Narratives

Another major contribution of the FIERCE Actions is their ability to renew the repertoires of political action by investing in alternative forms of expression –artistic, digital, sensory, capable of reaching marginalized audiences and those who are distant from traditional forms of engagement. These forms are not merely tools for raising awareness. They help to re-politicize everyday practices and challenge norms of visibility, legitimacy, and participation in the public sphere.

Far from being reduced to a logic of communication, or symbolic mobilisation, these Actions have implemented practices aimed at embodying alternative forms of political presence, particularly in contexts of marginalisation, censorship, and the criminalisation of feminist and LGBTQIA+ struggles. The use of activism (art + activism), digital technologies, collective performances, and the staging of bodily narratives have enabled certain collectives to create critical spaces where minority bodies, emotions, and affects are recognised as legitimate and important vectors of politicisation.

For example, the "Queer-Trans Feminist Cartoon" initiative (Turkey), led by Özgür Renkler Derneği, used comics as a tool for counter-narrative, enabling trans and queer people to make their experiences visible in a context of increasing censorship. By creating a space for narrative reappropriation, this Action has anchored political demands in creative and accessible forms of expression. Yet, the translation of these expressions into sustained political mobilizations remains uncertain and context dependent. Another example of activism in the FIERCE Actions is the "Orange Days" in Aalborg with several events focusing on preventing and combating gender-based violence organized by Centre for Violence Prevention, which included both street theatre performances and an art exhibition through the active engagement of survivors of gender-based violence telling their stories and providing experiential knowledge.

Some Actions have also activated the performative register of politics: The mobilisation of the body as a space of resistance has challenged prevailing norms of democratic representation. A noteworthy example is "The Musafir project" (Greece), combining visual arts, theatre and music, which explored the bodily memories of both exile and gender oppression. By adopting a sensory approach to resistance, this Action proposed another way of articulating the political, through lived experience, embodiment, and emotion – dimensions that are often excluded from formal political practices and can become re-legitimised by feminist approaches. It has been a main concern of several of the participants in The Musafir/Boat Collective project to diffuse this approach. However, while the embodied politics is a powerful approach, it takes a lot of time and risks remaining quantitatively limited in terms of the number of people it actually reaches, raising the question of how such forms can more widely circulate

and resonate beyond their initial setting without being diluted or misunderstood. A similar interpretation of the trade-offs regarding unpredictability and long-term sustainability can be made for any of these actions. Also, the action participants themselves saw a value in the activities because of their unpredictable outcomes. In other words, controlled uncertainty itself can be considered politically and culturally productive, because of the potential and promising effects it can generate.

Digital technology has also been a field of democratic experimentation. In a context where digital platforms are both tools for mobilisation and spaces for censorship or anti-feminist violence, several FIERCE Actions have used digital technology as a lever for resistance. The “Gender Debunking Guerilla” project led by *Fundacja Kocham Dębni* (Poland), for example, set up a gender equality awareness campaign and distributed resources on reproductive rights via QR codes placed in urban spaces, enabling the activists to circumvent censorship and reach a wider audience of women and migrant women anonymously and securely. In doing so, this Action reactivated the digital space as an arena for struggle, while reaching audiences far removed from traditional activism.

Similarly, the “LGBTQI+ Radar” platform of *Iniciativa TransAkcija* (Slovenia) has helped consolidate an online space for LGBTQIA+ and feminist self-organisation. It has contributed to structure a digital counter-power in the context of liberalisation of discourse and anti-gender attacks, experimenting with forms of self-management, resource sharing, and participatory governance. While used as a tool for mobilisation and community-building, the digital space functioned, in some cases, also as a site of democratic experimentation. Yet this potential remained uneven, particularly in those political contexts where online repression and algorithmic censorship limited both visibility and interaction.

Faced with the regression of women's and gender minority rights in several national contexts, these Actions combined activist knowledge, knowledge production, and public campaigns to influence political decisions. These initiatives have demonstrated that feminist advocacy is not just a matter of challenging public authorities but constitutes a genuine strategy for political influence, rooted in forms of grassroots and collective mobilisation. Nonetheless, the capacity to influence institutional agendas often depended on pre-existing access points or informal connections, underlining the unequal permeability of institutional spaces to feminist grassroots interventions.

Finally, some actions have redefined the domestic or community space as a place of politicisation, particularly around care, sharing, and food. The “Santa Chiara” initiative (Italy), by setting up a feminist collective kitchen, has made food a vehicle for solidarity and empowerment, valuing the knowledge of immigrant women and affirming their place in the local economy and the public sphere. In the same vein, several FIERCE Action groups have incorporated spaces for care and mutual support among activists into their projects. Faced with activist burnout, several collectives developed a diverse set of practices revolving around rest, sharing, and care inspired by feminist, Afro-descendant, and queer

traditions. These practices recognise the physical and emotional dimensions of struggle as integral components of political action. As one member of Savoir-Pouvoir points out in the post-action questionnaire: "Taking care of ourselves is also protecting our movement in the long term."

These repertoires of action, whether rooted in art, digital technology, care or community, have contributed, in various ways, to deepen the dynamics of and knowledge about democratic innovation initiated by the FIERCE Actions. Yet, their ability to produce broader outreach and sustained transformative impact remained, perhaps unsurprisingly, uneven. Much depended on factors such as cultural capital, technological literacy, access to safe physical as well as digital spaces — all of which varied significantly across the different political contexts. Taken together, however, these FIERCE Actions demonstrate that democracy is not only played out in formal institutions, but also in the concrete practices through which marginalised collectives and communities are reinventing the modalities of political participation and deliberation from the margins.

3.3. Successes, Limitations and Lessons from FIERCE Actions

A set of tangible contributions and major successes have been identified through the targeted survey on the FIERCE Actions. These findings are furthermore confirmed by a cross-country analysis of the empirical materials:

- **Strengthening alliances and activist networks:** Several actions, including Transfeminist Initiative TransAkcija in Slovenia that created a platform between queer and LGBTQAI+ activists in Slovenia and Kuir-Trans Feminist Karikatür Okulu which provided an opportunity for various LGBTQAI+ activists to work together on a concrete comic books project in Turkey have helped to consolidate and expand both feminist and LGBTQIA+ networks, promoting exchanges between territories, generations, activist profiles, and forms of action.
- **Production and circulation of political knowledge:** Many FIERCE Actions, including as Orange days in Aalborg in which a card game was designed (Denmark) and gender debunking guerilla which created QR codes stickers to inform about GBV and women's rights (Poland), have generated collective tools –manuals, digital platforms, games, artistic content– designed as training, transmission or advocacy materials. These tools embody a pedagogy of feminist action based on the sharing of situated knowledge.
- **Strengthening organisational capacities:** Several actions, including Women Worker Solidarity Association Workshop (Turkey) focussing on labour rights and feminism, which provided to work closely with labour unions about feminism and gender rights and Arti femministe a Santa Chiara (Italy) which worked with multiform skills sharing, such as cooking, have had direct impact on the structuring of the collectives involved. They have enabled the expansion of

activist bases, the acquisition of new skills (logistics, communication, project management), and access to additional funding.

- **The redefinition of political agendas**, which were sometimes reframed or expanded through collective deliberation or in reaction to external constraints, like for instance for *Savoirs-Pouvoir* (France), which increased the realm of the content covered by the training and *Akcja Aborcja* (Poland), which had to re-define their form of action in the face of political censorship in rural areas.

While some FIERCE Actions have strengthened their capacity for action of intersectional feminist collectives and revealed a tangible potential for democratic innovation, the Actions have also brought to light a set of limitations. Notably collectives have for instance suffered from internal conflicts, had difficulty accessing additional resources for their work or had difficulties implementing intersectionality, due to the limited availability of some participants. These limitations should not be understood as mere operational difficulties, but as the expression of structural dynamics: They remind us that feminist democratic innovations are carried out in spaces of persistent unequal power relations and that intersectional practices, far from self-evident, require specific conditions for implementation.

3.3.1. Differentiated Temporalities, Resources and Capacities

Several FIERCE Actions highlighted the tensions encountered within the limited timeframe for implementation – between November 2024 and March 2025. This timeline was created to develop pilot actions. However, it was identified retrospectively as a factor that limited the preparatory phases (mobilisation, territorial anchoring, and formalisation of partnerships) or made it difficult to integrate more complex participatory formats. In several cases, initial ambitions were scaled back to meet these constraints, leading to tactical refocusing on more ad hoc actions, sometimes experienced as a form of political compromise.

These difficulties echo Donatella della Porta's work on the differentiated temporalities of participatory democracy (2022), where bottom-up politicisation dynamics require spaces for maturation, disagreement, and collective reformulation. In several cases, there was indeed not enough time to establish genuine spaces for political co-construction, particularly when the target audiences were distant from existing activist networks or unfamiliar with participatory frameworks.

Beyond the time factor, disparities in resources led to inequalities in the capacity to implement Actions. While the FIERCE project made it possible to involve less institutionalised organisations, the limited resources provided (between 2000 and 3700 euros for the activity) revealed asymmetries between collectives, depending on their size, activist history, and ability to mobilise additional resources. In some cases, collectives with such resources financed part of the planned activities themselves or the collectives gave up some of the more ambitious aspects of their Action. As Ciccia and Roggeband (2021)

point out, intersectional feminist organisations, particularly those from minority groups –racialised women, migrants, queer women, precarious workers– face structural barriers to accessing funding, technical skills, and institutional networks. These inequalities directly affect their political room for manoeuvring. Several also mentioned the lack of human resources to realise the Actions (relying mainly on volunteers) and specific skills (in project management, communication, digital tools), which may have led to unbalanced workloads, tensions, exhaustion, or partial disengagement. These tensions have tested the principles of horizontality, power-sharing, and co-responsibility that most Actions claimed to uphold.

These findings invite us to look beyond any short-term interpretation. They point to a more general condition of contemporary intersectional feminist movements: a massive reliance on volunteering, activist emotion, and multiple commitments, which are often invisible or insufficiently recognised in participatory mechanisms. They echo the theoretical critiques formulated by Crenshaw (1989) and Collins (2000) on the invisibility of emotional and logistical work in feminist movements. Voluntary engagement, while enabling agile and flexible forms of action, also exposes collectives to forms of ‘over-responsibilisation’, particularly when invisible care and logistical work are disproportionately borne by certain members. This dynamic, often gendered and racialised, complicates the effective implementation of horizontal governance and raises critical questions about sustainability.

While this configuration opens flexible spaces for experimentation, it also exposes participants to forms of self-exploitation or activist burnout, compromising the sustainability of collective dynamics. In post-Action feedback, several collectives emphasised the importance of better anticipating the distribution of responsibilities, formalising governance tools, and recognising the different contributions of members according to their social positions. This need for clarification and real redistribution of power in activist spaces echoes a central requirement of intersectional democratic innovation: that of recognising the concrete conditions under which power is exercised, including within collectives, and acting deliberately to address them.

In several contexts, FIERCE Actions have faced explicit or latent forms of political hostility that have limited their reach, visibility or implementation. These obstacles have manifested themselves in both public arenas and digital spaces. In Poland, the workshop initially planned in Gardeja was cancelled following the withdrawal of municipal support, despite the mayor's personal support for reproductive rights. In Turkey, the organisers of the "Women's Rights to Work " Action encountered difficulties in securing an independent space for their activities, revealing how the material organisation of a feminist event can be a political issue in itself. These experiences, far from being marginal, reveal the structural tensions surrounding intersectional feminist action: uncertain access to venues, withdrawal of fragile

institutional support, fear of reprisals. They remind us that even when rights are officially recognised, their implementation remains vulnerable to control, delegitimisation or silent withdrawal.

Some Actions also experienced digital censorship. In Poland, several of the publications of the project were restricted or removed from digital platforms, particularly those addressing sexual violence or reproductive rights. These forms of algorithmic censorship, which are difficult to challenge, reveal the implicit norms that govern the circulation of feminist discourse in digital spaces. They reinforce existing barriers to the visibility of actions, particularly when they take a critical stance towards institutions, heteronormative norms or conservative nationalism.

3.3.2. Intersectionality: Between a Shared Political Horizon and Difficult Practices

All FIERCE Actions have advocated an intersectional feminist approach, seeking to articulate power relations linked to gender, class, race, sexuality, disability, and migration status. This common orientation is an important political achievement: It reflects the spread of critical frameworks developed from the margins and a collective desire to decentre democratic analysis based on minority experiences. However, the concrete implementation of intersectionality has proven to be complex, marked by tensions, unthought-through aspects and sometimes painful adjustments, which the Action leaders themselves identified in their post-Action feedback.

In several Actions, collectives highlighted the gap between their initial intersectional intentions and the actual effects of the projects. Recurring difficulties were reported in sustainably involving certain individuals or groups —migrant women, trans people, racialised people, people with disabilities or without legal status— whom the Actions explicitly aimed to integrate. This gap was often attributed to material and timescale obstacles (e.g., language barriers and lack of time to build trust), but also to internal asymmetries: unequal access to speaking opportunities, priority setting, or decision-making capacity.

In several contexts, intersectoral alliances designed as levers for emancipation have revealed deep tensions, including within supposedly allied circles. In Turkey, for example, the "Women's Rights at Work" campaign led by *Kadın İşçi* encountered fundamental disagreements with partner trade unions, whose priorities remained focused on a more androcentric approach to work. This divergence in the interpretation of gender issues limited the possibilities for strategic convergence and served as a reminder that activist spaces themselves are not free from power relations. Intersectionality cannot be thought of as a simple inclusive expansion: It involves a shift in political centres of gravity and, in its implementation, requires ongoing political negotiation, the dismantling of power relations, and the reformulation of priorities based on the voices of minority groups.

These internal tensions, which are sometimes more difficult to anticipate than institutional obstacles, highlight the importance of thinking about frameworks for cooperation not as givens, but as spaces of

tension. They remind us that, to be effective, intersectionality requires explicit mechanisms for safety, recognition, and power-sharing — including among allies.

Other collectives have faced internal conflicts around intersectional practices. In some actions, imbalances in commitment or recognition have strained the principles of horizontality that were being claimed. The lack of shared governance tools, unevenly distributed mental load, and the absence of collective mediation have contributed to the emergence of feelings of injustice or marginalisation within groups. These dynamics, often addressed reflectively in reviews, show that intersectionality is not limited to identifying intersecting oppressions, as Kimberlé Crenshaw argues: It aims to transform the political and legal systems that produce them by revealing institutional blind spots.

Rather than an abstract horizon or a discursive label, intersectionality appears in FIERCE Actions as a demanding political practice — at once epistemic, organisational, and relational. Its effective implementation requires long timeframes, spaces for legitimate disagreement, listening mechanisms, and explicit mechanisms for redistributing power. In this regard, several collectives have expressed the need to consolidate intersectional frameworks of engagement beyond the temporality of the Action by developing specific tools: internal charters, shared governance guides, and spaces for political review of alliances. These elements confirm Patricia Hill Collins' contributions on the need to translate subaltern knowledge into sustainable collective practices rooted in relationships of reciprocity, accountability, and mutual recognition (Collins, 2000).

The FIERCE Actions have thus demonstrated that intersectionality is not a given, but a hard-won achievement, constantly reworked by the concrete conditions of action, persistent asymmetries, and the political negotiations it imposes. By revealing these tensions, they remind us that democratic innovation cannot be separated from careful attention to social relations and power practices that permeate even alternative spaces.

3.4. Concluding Remarks

The FIERCE Actions as a whole reveal how intersectional feminist democratic innovation is both a shared political horizon and a testing ground. While collectives have demonstrated their capacity to produce grounded, inventive, and solidarity-based forms of action, they have also highlighted the structural tensions that run through activist spaces: asymmetries in resources, time and economic constraints, political tensions, and internal power relations. These tensions should not be seen as failures, but as markers of a demanding field of experimentation, where promises of participation, equality, and recognition are confronted with social and political realities. By revealing the complexity of putting intersectionality into practice, the FIERCE Actions remind us that reinventing democracy from the margins requires specific conditions of support, temporality, and redistribution of power.

Despite these constraints, the FIERCE Actions have generated concrete political learning effects. They have made it possible to test new organisational forms and repertoires of action; produce alternative narratives; and experiment with the mobilisation of unlikely alliances. Tools designed in a local or temporary context have found unexpected extensions: dissemination in schools, reappropriation by other groups, reformulation of objectives. This ability to transcend their initial format demonstrates a profound transformative potential. These effects confirm the hypothesis that feminist democratic innovation is not limited to the creation of new institutional mechanisms but lies in the ability of collectives to reconfigure the rules of the political game from the margins – by combining criticism, care, imagination, self-determination, emotions, and engagement. In this sense, FIERCE Actions are not only situated experiences of democratic transformation, but also critical spaces for experimenting with the political democratic forms of tomorrow.

4. Democratic Innovations in Country Case Studies

This chapter analyses feminist democratic innovations across the eight country cases (Denmark, France, Greece, Italy, Poland, Slovenia, Spain, Turkey) as well as at trans-European level, with particular attention to the political implications for the future of feminism in Europe. The chapter complements the analyses of feminist democratic innovations carried out in the National and Transnational Labs and in the FIERCE Actions, as discussed in the sections above. These initiatives strived to enact intersectional approaches to feminist activism, to organise critical counter publics, and to engage in novel forms of knowledge production (see Chapter 2 and 3). Here we build instead on the results of a collaborative exchange among the FIERCE partners, driven by the aim of identifying key findings on feminist democratic innovations emerging from all the empirical streams of the FIERCE project (critical frame analysis; discourse network analysis; interviews) and informed by the partners' expertise on the specific sociopolitical contexts.

During the process of collaborative exchange, all partners contributed to the elaboration of nine internal reports on feminist democratic innovations across the eight country cases and at the trans-European level. These reports were based on the results from the three empirical streams but also included reflections on the National Labs and FIERCE Actions. To ensure an alignment of analytical approaches and theoretical understandings, all partners were encouraged to read a preliminary version of our literature review (Chapter 1). Furthermore, the case studies were elaborated on the basis of eight questions that were formulated by a working group. These questions touch upon four overlapping themes that have been discussed and assessed to be essential for the inquiry into feminist democratic innovations: 1) Inclusion and exclusion in democratic political spaces; 2) Intersectionality and power dynamics; 3) Alternative imaginaries and protest forms; and 4) Feminist knowledge production and the relations between activists and scholars. These four themes reflect the different types of feminist democratic innovation identified in the literature review (see Chapter 1). The questions are listed below:

1. Does your material indicate innovations aimed at increasing and/or supporting the participation of women, including women from different minority groups, in institutional politics and/or activism? If so, what do such innovations constitute, and how do they emerge?
2. Do feminist movement practices and mobilizations challenge one or more of the three powerful political logics identified by Jone Martínez-Palacios, which are: 1) Delegitimizing private matters; 2) Devaluing relational-emotional arguments; and 3) Enforcing a universal mode of political participation? If so, how do they do so?
3. Did you observe any participation from feminist movements/civil society to "invited spaces," i.e., mini-publics, participatory budget, citizen juries? If so, how were their experiences and did the participation have an "agonistic counterpublic" feature?

4. Can you trace any forms of alternative imaginaries of democracy and alternative practices developed by feminist movements/activists that point at emerging feminist prefigurative politics?
5. Does your material show feminist movements promoting innovative/alternative forms of protest/mobilization/decision making compared with other social movements? If yes, how?
6. Can you detect forms of intersectional solidarity to address power disparities in the way in which issues are framed, met by an equally deep transformation of the material structures through which power works within?
7. How do you consider that the collaboration and power dynamics/relations between feminist movements and feminist academics/experts from within the Lab contributed to knowledge production? Did you observe new ways to frame and shape it? Did pre-determined roles/power structures prevail, or were these challenged? Which elements of the FIERCE Action generated in your Lab pointed at novel elements based on your context, which can be related to the feminist democratic innovation sketched out in the text? Do the identified feminist democratic innovations challenge the existing literature and scholarly debate on democratic innovations? If so, how?
8. Looking at your findings on feminist mobilizations from the angle of feminist knowledge production to counteract anti-gender discourse (and their knowledge production): Do you see specific instances of relevant research/media production or other explicit action to generate evidence/evidence-based arguments against the attacks from anti-gender/anti-democratic actors?

4.1. Five Types of Democratic Innovation

Even though feminist movements across Europe are still predominately reactive and defensive in response to anti-gender and anti-feminist backlash, our results indicate that many activists succeed in proactively developing and experimenting with new democratic practices, often with a prefigurative aim of shaping inclusionary and horizontal relations through the organization of their work. Returning to the typology that was presented in the first chapter (see pp. 15-21), the analysis of the empirical results from our case studies indicates that all four types of feminist democratic innovation (Promoting women's rights and participation; Creating subaltern counter-publics; Enacting intersectional approaches; Engaging in feminist knowledge production) are practiced in varying degrees and ways within the different national and transnational contexts. Yet, a fifth type of democratic innovation, *hybrid activism*, emerged from the empirical findings across the contexts. In the following, we provide a cross-country overview of the different democratic innovations, adding key examples to illustrate them. Together with the previous chapters on the co-creation Labs and the FIERCE Actions, this will

provide the basis for the final chapter that discusses the potentials and limits of democratic innovations for feminist movements in Europe with specific recommendations being offered, considering both the difficulties and the tensions in innovating democracy in practice from a feminist perspective.

4.1.1. Promoting Women's Rights and Participation

The social and political empowerment of women, and in particular minoritized and marginalised women, is a recurrent focus across the analysed cases. This often entails recognizing diversity and practicing inclusion, critically approaching universal framings that tend to portray women as a homogeneous group. For instance, the feminist movement in Turkey increasingly supports rural women in their resistance against different energy projects, such as mining and dams across the Turkish countryside, a struggle that strongly connects to eco-feminist practices (Erol 2025; Yaka 2017). In several well-known cases, rural women have themselves stood up for rights, challenging authorities at public hearings and meetings, aiming to prevent the environmental destruction that such projects mean for the local communities (Yavuz & Şendeniz, 2013), particularly under the Environmental Impact Assessment procedure. In Spain, care workers with a migrant background have mobilized to protest the live-in care regime and to promote the recognition of care work and the dignity of their profession. In Poland, there have been pro-turnout campaigns as a run-up to recent elections, targeting particularly women and young people with the motivational slogan “You vote – you decide”. This while grassroots Women's Councils have been established in local governments. Before the parliamentary elections in 2023, a campaign called “Women for the 2023 Elections” was launched, which was an apolitical social campaign organized by the *Moc Kobiet* (“Power of Women”) Foundation, aiming to encourage specifically women to participate in the elections. Furthermore, in the context of the 2023 elections, there was a significant increase in the number of women candidates and MPs, which was also the result of the greater involvement of women in public debate and of the political parties' strategy to appeal directly to women's claims and rights. Such examples epitomize how promoting an agenda with women's political rights and active participation in society at the forefront is a type of feminist activism still demanding innovative ideas, transversal alliances, and the discussion of how to give subalterns a voice.

Among the cases analysed, Slovenia stands out as a model for the feminist movements' sustained commitment to increasing the participation of women, particularly those from marginalized and minority groups. One striking example is the feminist direct social action during the so-called “migrant crisis” in 2015, where autonomous feminist spaces supported the self-organization of migrant women and served as hubs for anti-racist mobilization. These initiatives included peer-to-peer support networks prioritizing solidarity, care and engagement. Another notable case is the transnational solidarity fostered by anarcho-feminist groups in response to the Russia-Ukrainian war. Collaborating with feminist collectives in Ukraine and Poland, Slovenian activists organized fundraising initiatives and

supplied emergency contraceptives to women affected by the war. These efforts demonstrate a form of prefigurative politics “here and now”, striving to enact the values of inclusive democratic society not only in-situ, but also elsewhere, where action is most needed. Through such practices, feminist actors address urgent needs and learn how to expand democratic agency by practicing forms of mutual solidarity, care, and shared responsibility across the borders.

Similarly, in Italy, feminist activists have provided numerous examples of democratic innovations aimed at enhancing the participation of women, including those from marginalized backgrounds. While direct access to institutional politics remains limited to all, feminist actors are reconfiguring activism as a political space in its own right. They do so by fostering horizontal decision-making, inclusive educational practices, and collective care mechanisms. These practices are particularly evident in feminist networks engaged in school education, anti-violence programs, and reproductive justice. At the same time, feminist activists are aware that the activist spaces are not fully inclusive. As an example, it can be difficult for mothers to participate in assemblies organized late in the evening, or for workers, to gather too early in the day. Most activists show ongoing reflectivity on the issue of exclusion and inclusion, not least because of the intersectional perspective that have become dominant in the Italian feminist movement since the mid-2010s.

In Greece, feminist initiatives such as the IAmNotADoll campaign, which uses an interactive exhibition of sculptures to raise awareness and highlight that beauty does not make someone an object or a doll, are often coordinated by young women, including LGBTQ+ and immigrant voices. These campaigns bypass mainstream media and recalibrate the narratives around lived experience, reflecting a growing, female-led cultural shift driven by online activism. Social media campaigns, digital storytelling, and grassroots organizing have amplified marginalized voices, enabling decentralized leadership and cross-movement solidarity. These spaces have allowed queer women, migrant activists, and working-class feminists to frame violence not as isolated acts, but as outcomes of interconnected systems of power and exclusion. Thus, this digital and grassroots momentum has reframed gender-based violence as a structural issue — one that demands system-wide change rather than tokenistic reforms.

4.1.2. Creating Counterpublics

(Subaltern) counterpublics, as another type of feminist democratic innovation, were created in the National and Transnational Labs by challenging the logics of participation and ‘reasonableness’ that often permeate mainstream publics and the way in which deliberation practices are conducted and institutionalised. This is, for instance, highlighted in the case of the Transnational Lab, where the participants emphasized the importance of emotions and mutual care, focusing on balancing political engagement with personal well-being. The National Labs and the FIERCE Actions also provided novel opportunities for reorganization, safe spaces, and solidarity in times of intense backlash from anti-

feminist and anti-gender actors, particularly in contexts such as Poland, Turkey, and Italy. The Italian feminist movement in particular has in recent years enacted and experimented with open assemblies and consensus-based processes, which have contributed to the creation of more inclusive and resilient counter-publics across the country.

It is worth noting that feminist counterpublics are not to be understood as isolated from other public settings but, in many cases, they are organized with the explicit purpose of carefully intervening in mainstream public debate, with forceful messages and creative protests, happenings, and spaces of reflection. This was, for instance, the case in Denmark where the social media campaign which was organized through the National Lab focused on sexism against minorities with the aim of sensitising public opinion on the lack of attention, research, and resources related to the problem of how sexism targets and affects minorities. Similarly in the Slovenian case, the outcome of the National Labs was an exhibition on reproductive rights in the public space, which was planned as a strategic feminist intervention. The feminist festival in France, *Les Marges en Feu!* (“Margins on Fire”), in 2025 was also organized with the explicit aim to facilitate an open space for feminist counterpublics through, for instance, an inclusive citizen’s assembly, which brought forward voices that are often marginalized in mainstream French public discourse.

Counterpublics prove particularly effective in fostering political practices in contexts heavily affected by democratic backlash. In Turkey, the co-creation Labs and the feminist mobilization created vital spaces for mutual support, spreading joy and hope for change in critical moments for democracy and gender equality. Interviews with feminist activists revealed that external constraints on activism can become internalised when individual lives are under pressure, but also that emotion work in feminist gatherings help sustain community resilience and proactivity within movements and grassroots. Activists emphasized the feelings of pride and self-acknowledgment for defending rights and empowering minorities in a political climate where other movements seem to have taken several steps backwards from the public sphere. At the same time, the interviews underlined the personal toll that the struggle can take on feminist activists, with increasing emotional strain and enhanced feelings of insecurity and self-exposure. Especially Kurdish feminist and LGBTQI+ activists shared their thoughts about leaving the country. To fight back, some activists described how emotion work has become an integral part of everyday organizing. For instance, in internal meetings, feminists make explicit efforts to show care toward one another, sharing what makes them feel good (or bad, so that the person ‘gets it out of their system’). In addition, some groups have added to their repertoire of action cultural political events, aimed at sustaining “feminist joy.” In fact, when asked, some Turkish interviewees plainly stated that the thing they do best is “to organize fun.”

Counterpublics are often portrayed as a form of unified, homogeneous form of political resistance in “oppositional stance” towards mainstream publics. However, as demonstrated by the examples above, counterpublics can provide space for constructive critique between the participants and also a space to express and deal with internal disagreement. This is, for instance, the case of the Transnational Lab, which aimed at creating a political outcome to counteract the effects of the anti-gender backlash. The Lab approach was to design a space of “critical friendship” between FIERCE partners and activists. This notion, as defined by Costa and Kallick (1993), describes trusted peers who offer constructive critique of alternative and perhaps competing perspectives. Chappell and Mackay (2021) reinterpret “critical friends” in feminist terms as researchers aligned with feminist agendas, but positioned at a distance, offering reflective insights. During the Transnational Lab, power balancing efforts were made to ensure that activists’ needs, expectations, and constraints would be taken into account from the beginning and that all participants contributed on equal terms to the development and implementation of the FIERCE campaign. Even if the Lab did not entirely succeed in this because some participants still felt less heard than others, the Transnational Lab as a counterpublic was meant to provide a space for a diversity of voices and internal critique from all participants. Similarly, other feminist counterpublics across Europe may also face challenges in practicing equality and facilitating a genuine space for internal disagreement, but most often there is an explicit promotion of such features.

4.1.3. The Integral Role of Intersectionality

Intersectionality plays a central role in feminist democratic innovations. It was central, for instance, to the feminist strikes in Spain and Italy, as well as in the autonomous feminist spaces created during the 2015 ‘migrant crisis’ in Slovenia. Feminist activism in Greece also provides notable and inspiring examples of how to integrate feminist and LGBTQ+ perspectives. Trans-feminist collectives and feminist NGOs such as the *Diotima Centre* incorporate a strong and explicitly intersectional approach to their activities. As an example of concrete collaboration showcasing this form of integration, Amnesty International Greece and Transgender Support Association (GTSA) have in recent years started to collaborate and combine human rights discourse with queer and trans feminist activism, resulting in novel framings of structural discrimination. Intersectional ideas and practices reshape feminist activism by broadening its scope and promoting diversity and inclusiveness in the struggle for equality, thereby positioning intersectionality as one of the key drivers of democratic innovation.

At the same time, the FIERCE findings reveal challenges and internal divisions over how intersectionality should be understood. These tensions give rise to contested visions regarding the broad meaning of gender identity and sexual orientation, and in particular regarding the groups that ought to be included within the feminist project. This was revealed at the transnational European level where polarization and challenges to intersectionality emerged within transnational feminist advocacy networks: Intersectionality was fully part of the self-definition for some actors, focusing on structural oppressions

and inclusion of LGBTIQ+, transpersons, and sex workers, whereas other actors instead tended to prioritize specific axes of discrimination (i.e., age, disability) over others and sex-based rights over “gender.” Referring to the concern that “women” are de-prioritized on political agendas, self-defined feminist NGOs in certain cases endorsed arguments that are close to those disseminated by anti-gender, TERF actors.

However, concrete practices showed intersectionality at work. In the Spanish case, for instance, marginalised groups like migrant domestic workers and LGBTIQ+ persons constitute themselves as the core of influential feminist collectives and as such embody the work on intersectionality. Ongoing collaborations between feminist groups and collectives of domestic and care workers, dissident migrants, and racialized communities are expressions of intersectionality in practice, with some collectives having established dedicated structures to this, such as the Migration and Antiracism Commission composed of racialized and migrant members. The participation of racialised and migrant women helps to ensure that intersectional perspectives inform both discussions and deliberations. As a Spanish feminist activist remarked: “Just the fact that they are there makes intersectionality present in some way” (A_FA4). Several other Spanish interviewees underlined that defending LGBTIQ+ rights is integral to their feminist work and resistance. This did not mean that tensions and conflicts were not present in the Spanish context; several interviewees also reflected on tensions related to the (lack of) voice and presence in feminist activism of, for example, racialised women and transgender people.

4.1.4. Feminist Knowledge Production

Feminist knowledge production is the fourth type of democratic innovation identified in the literature and also recurrent in the different national and transnational contexts studied in the FIERCE project. For example, Greece provides a paradigmatic case of how knowledge production can become central to feminist democratic innovations with feminist NGOs and grassroots activists co-producing knowledge on gender-based violence and oppression of LGBTIQ+ people with involvement of both scholars and activists. Also, the Greek NGO *Diotima Centre* specializes in preventing and combating gender-based violence by combining academic expertise with community-based practices and narratives from survivors. Similarly, after the 2020 Constitutional Tribunal ruling which further restricted access to abortion in Greece, feminist activists focused on publishing personal testimonies of abortion experiences and forced pregnancies, as appeals to empathy and as knowledge sharing about the concrete implications of the abortion legislation.

In the Danish case, feminist knowledge production also proved to be effective in a recent campaign promoting consent-based rape legislation, which was passed in 2020, and in the case of mobilizations demanding equal pay for female-dominated health care professions. In these two campaigns, several academics with expertise on the issues were involved and used their voice and ‘authority’ in public to strengthen the feminist claims and support the mobilizations. In the case of the successful campaign for

a consent-based rape legislation, this became obvious in the collaboration between a national coalition of feminist organizations and the legal scholar Trine Baumbach, who together sought to argue for the theoretical and practical distinctions between a rape legislation based on the principle of voluntariness and legislation based on consent as the core principle. In the case of the campaign for equal pay, grassroots activists and trade unions collaborated with historians to argue that the Public Servant Reform Act of 1969 was an outdated law maintaining gender inequality. Renown intellectuals participated in public protests, wrote opinion pieces, and signed statements to spread awareness and knowledge among the public about the historical foundations behind unequal pay.

As a result of feminist knowledge production, there is often a blurring of boundaries between activism and expertise with many activists also being educators and researchers. Instead of having pre-determined roles when, for instance, elaborating evidence-based counterarguments to attacks from anti-gender actors, the emphasis is on horizontal forms of exchange and mutual learning. The National Labs were also designed spaces of “critical friendship”, where participants were encouraged to contribute with their perspectives and insights, while also offering constructive critique in the co-creative process, and where power hierarchies between academic/non-academic knowledge production were at play and reflectively challenged.

4.1.5. Hybrid Activism

Finally, it has become clear through a cross-cutting comparison of our findings from the national and transnational contexts, that a fifth type of feminist democratic innovation ought to be added to the previous four. We have labelled this *hybrid activism*. It includes feminist political practices that are distinctively hybrid in their communicative styles, target groups, and tools of mobilizations, thereby creating in-between spaces of feminist politics beyond the usual dichotomic categorizations, such as for example being either independent or collaborative with the political system, or contrasting rational argumentation language with affective/emotional/creative language and media. Hybrid activism can become manifest in different forms that share the common trait of cutting across traditional ways of practicing, as well as theorizing, activism by creatively combining them. In this sense, hybrid activism is about practicing feminism in the form of a novel mixture of approaches and forms of expression that are usually conceived as being opposite to each other. There can be different strategic purposes for doing so, for instance that traditional types of political communication are considered to be less effective in a certain context, or that the usual repertoire of action does not reach the desired audiences. This provides an occasion for mixing different forms of activism, such as merging a panel debate with an artistic performance or combining grassroots protest with political lobbyism.

Hybrid activism stood out as a novel feature in the analysis of the feminist movements across the eight country cases. For instance, in the Slovenian case, hybrid activism emerged from the co-existence of institutional and grassroots approaches within the feminist movement, allowing feminist activists to

contest the political system as a whole, while also leveraging various ‘practicable’ institutional mechanisms and, at least to some extent, ‘playing the game’ through institutionalized channels. The use of hybrid activism is also recurrently reflected in communication styles, where the feminist movement in Italy stands out for applying rational and institutional language at the same time as they express feelings of hope, empathy, and solidarity. Similarly, during the campaign for marriage equality in 2015, the Slovenian feminist movement combined affective communication and the sharing of personal experiences with rational and juridical argumentation. In this manner, their rhetoric did not fit into a simple analytical box but involved a complex interplay between, for instance, scientific references and direct emotional appeals. Hybrid activism is, thus, about challenging or evading well-established norms and categories, and it allows for a broader exploration into new potential avenues (communicative, actionable, etc.) that can reach and influence different publics and settings.

Several forms of democratic innovation embody different aspects of hybrid activism in that they challenge established norms and categories. Intersectional approaches, for instance, often entail explicit critique of how mainstream discourse frames gender (in)equality and other social justice issues through rigid, separate categories of identification. Feminist knowledge production further illustrates hybridity by blurring boundaries between activism and academic scholarship, political engagement and supposedly ‘neutral’ research. This challenges the idea of activism as purely immediate action/reaction, as well as the notion that scholars must distance themselves from politics to avoid biases or to fit research into predetermined political objectives. In this sense, hybrid activism operates as a form of experimentation and as a laboratory for expanded avenues of democratic innovation, reminding us that innovation can disrupt entrenched ways of engaging with politics and publics.

Hybrid activism was also present in the Turkish case through alternative and atypical forms of participation, such as protests and flash-mobs organized at night in spontaneous or unexpected places; campaigns during pandemic lockdowns; digital feminist campaigns like *“Istanbul Convention Keeps Us Alive”*; and creative performances appealing to emotions such as the country wide protests including the *“Las Tesis”* dance and poem. The slogans of the Feminist Night Marches directly criticized the public-private divide, body politics, and gender hierarchies and can be considered as a form of egalitarian democratic discourse that is, at the same time, hybrid in the sense of not following the usual standards of ‘rational’ public argumentation and not belonging to a private, domestic sphere. The slogans were: *“the private is political,” “this crowd is your home,” “you will never walk alone,” “I am the rebel daughter of my mother,” “we do not owe men a ‘moderate resistance’,” “the women do not need a mediator, but demand equality,”* and *“stop tiptoeing; let them wake up.”* The slogans express radical political critique communicated to the outside, but at the same time the aim is to build community internally among the activists, in solidarity with each other.

European-level feminist NGOs and umbrella organisations, such as the European Women’s Lobby, tend to focus primarily on lobbying towards EU-level institutional decision-making institutions. In contrast to this institutionalized approach, the E.A.S.T. transnational network stands out for its non-formalized status as an NGO when compared to most other EU-level NGOs; it mirrors grassroots mobilisation strategies used by national feminist movements, such as strikes and street protests, often carried out in alliance with other social movements. However, there are also networks and organizations that participate in institutional arenas while maintaining a more critical, reflective stance. This resembles forms of agonistic democratic innovations and “watchdogging”, challenging policy proposals from the EU institutions by constantly bringing the perspectives of feminist grassroots organizations to the forefront (e.g., WIDE+ and Young Feminist Europe). These actors practice hybrid activism at the EU level by combining grassroots campaigning and broader mobilization efforts with advocacy and lobbying instead of following an insider/outsider logic.

4.2. Concluding Remarks

The analysis of the eight case studies and the trans-European level shows that feminist movements across Europe are continuously experimenting with democratic innovation in different ways. All five elaborated types of feminist democratic innovation are present in most country cases, even if there are political circumstances and distinctive features about the movements which result in different approaches and focus points. For instance, the creation of counterpublics proved to be highly valuable and relevant in political contexts such as Poland and Turkey where authorities are more actively attacking feminist movements. Intersectionality, as a theoretical perspective and a distinct way of approaching politics, is more prevalent in Southern Europe than elsewhere with the feminist movements in countries such as Spain and Italy explicitly adopting transfeminist, anticapitalist, and antiracist positions. Across the different cases, however, contemporary feminist movements are showing their dynamic and evolving character, which the fifth type of feminist democratic innovation, hybrid activism, particularly testifies to as a way of venturing into the unknown, deliberately mixing different forms of communication and political practice in efforts to gain more outreach. Thus, it is likely that new types of feminist democratic innovation will emerge in the coming years.

5. Discussion and Conclusion

This final chapter of the report reflects on the key dimensions emerging from the analysis of the feminist democratic innovations conducted in the chapters above, in light of the democratic innovation trajectories delineated in the critical state of the art (see Chapter 1). Overall, the previous three chapters on the FIERCE Labs, FIERCE Actions, and the eight country cases as well as the European level have highlighted in various ways that feminist movements across Europe are continuously developing and experimenting with democratic innovation. The findings also show that there are distinctly *feminist* approaches to democratic innovation such as enacting intersectionality and facilitating subaltern counterpublics. At the same time, feminist movements experience serious challenges in countering both internal and external power dynamics, while limitations in resources have a negative impact on the possibilities of developing and expanding novel feminist practices. Building on such complexity, four central dimensions emerge as decisive for understanding the feminist contributions to democratic innovation in terms of dynamics and challenges.

5.1. Key dimensions of Feminist Democratic Innovation

5.1.1. Feminist Infrastructures of Solidarity

Organizational structures and processes play a decisive role in shaping feminist democratic innovations. How and where feminists meet and organize influence the potentials and consolidation of democratic innovations. As highlighted in earlier chapters, transformative and intersectional solidarity require sustained effort, time, and consistency for feminist organizations to confront power disparities, include marginalized groups, and influence decision making processes (see also Ciccina & Roggeband, 2021).

The National Labs, the FIERCE Actions, and interviews with feminist actors showcased many inspiring examples of such efforts. Over time, strong feminist and LGBTQ+ groups and alliances in Greece, Italy, and Spain have developed and established networks and coalitions, which provide safe arenas to address questions of gender, identity, and sexuality in the face of the shared threat from anti-gender and anti-feminist movements. Other innovative practices include the creation of digital platforms in several countries as a way of sharing strategies, tools, and organizational knowledge to resist and counter anti-gender and anti-feminist dynamics. The LGBTQI+ Radar platform of *Iniciativa TransAkcija* in Slovenia exemplifies this trend: It offers a digital space for feminist and LGBTQ+ self-organization, acting as a form of counter-power and a site of democratic experimentation and exchange.

At the same time, feminist organizing is impacted by constraints. These include, most notably, uneven access to time, financial, and human resources, as well as varying degrees of institutionalisation and formal network support. The co-creation Labs revealed significant inequalities not only between FIERCE partners and the invited activists but also among activist groups themselves, ranging from well-funded national organizations to entirely volunteer-driven collectives and grassroots initiatives. These resource

gaps have long affected voluntary-based activism yet addressing them at different levels remains critical for sustaining innovation.

Some promising practices to address this problem were suggested and discussed during the FIERCE project. For instance, the French Lab introduced the idea of “à la carte investment,” allowing participants to engage at different levels according to their capacity. Another of the suggested approaches was to avoid ‘extractivist’ dynamics by ensuring that all participants, particularly less-resourced groups, can benefit tangibly from their involvement in the Labs and Actions.

Our findings show that intersectional solidarity is a key dimension of feminist contributions to democratic innovation; this is reflected in practice through networks, coalitions, and platforms attending to a diversity of inequalities. It requires solidary attention to resource differences as well increased funding to ensure the sustainability of the various types of feminist democratic innovation.

5.1.2. Feminist Counterpublics and Visibility

Public outreach and visibility prove essential in how feminist democratic innovations can develop. Contemporary feminist movements are continuously experimenting with their public presence through, for instance, the creation of counterpublics and creative campaigns. In this sense, feminist counterpublics are both sites of preparation and experimentation with creative forms of public outreach and spaces of withdrawal, providing the activists with new energy and confidence.

Throughout the FIERCE project, it has become clear that counterpublics constitute promising avenues for exploring and collaborating on novel forms of feminist activism and engaging critically with implicit and explicit norms in mainstream publics. In the National Labs and FIERCE Actions, there are many examples of creative forms of public outreach, ranging from feminist exhibition on reproductive rights in Slovenia and gender equality awareness campaign with public QR codes in Poland, to the creation of queer comics in Turkey and migrant storytelling in Greece (see chapter 2 and 3 above). It is particularly important for marginalized groups and voices to come forward and take active part in such public outreach activities, which is also a recurrent focus for the examined feminist movements. For instance, the National Labs in Denmark involved campaigns on sexism from a minority perspective with engagement from activists with various minority backgrounds, particularly LGBTQ+, disabled, and racialized people. In this way, intersectionality does not remain an internal and confined organizational principle for feminist activists only, but also a structuring element in how they approach being visible in public and a practice involving continuous learning for both activists and others in the public sphere.

A continuous and serious concern related to the co-creation Labs was that some of the forums were predominately thought for activist exchange and collaboration, heightening the risk of becoming secluded and self-affirming instead of being open to internal disagreement and engaging critically with other publics. Indeed, a counterpublic is meant to have porous boundaries in an agonistic but

continuous relational exchange to other publics. In many of the FIERCE Labs, it was therefore perceived as essential to have a wider public outreach, with the safer space within the Lab setting being considered a steppingstone towards creative public interventions carried out through, for instance, the Actions.

Thus, developing counterpublics and creative forms of public outreach hold potential as transformative forms of feminist democratic innovation with a wider impact, not least when being mindful of engaging directly with intersectional concerns and practices while also attending to internal disagreements.

5.1.3. Feminist Engagement with Institutions

Another of the key dimensions emerging through the analysis of feminist democratic innovations is the powerful role of the political system and its relation to feminist movements. This is a crucial factor in the formation of most feminist democratic innovations, even though innovation can also take place in civil society without this being directly connected to any political institution as such. Indeed, proximity to the political system and the path dependency of, for instance, receiving financial support from the state as an NGO may hinder the development of democratic innovation, even if democratic innovation does not necessarily arise from positioning oneself at a distance from political institutions either.

Most promising in regard to feminist engagement with political institutions is the way in which hybrid activism lays the ground for feminist democratic innovations and a different approach to civil society/state interactions. Here, hybridity means refusing to accept an inside/outside dichotomy regarding the feminist movements' interactions with institutions. In Greece and Italy, this has developed into an explicit feminist position seeking to engage with institutions in 'oblique' ways, approaching democracy as both pragmatic collaboration and agonistic politics that can also radically challenge the basic structures of society such as liberal capitalism. In Turkey as another case in point, alliances between a wide range of different societal actors have brought more leverage into the interactions with the state and helped to promote policies that might otherwise have been difficult to address. The FIERCE Action "Women's Rights to Work", which involved cooperation between activists, lawyers, trade unionists, and journalists, provides a good example of this form of wide-ranging alliance-building.

However, as the case studies also seem to suggest, there might not be any ideal balance between either staying at a complete distance from political institutions or becoming fully cooperative without much room for critique. In some contexts, the political system is certainly more receptive and cooperative vis-à-vis feminist proposals and campaigns, as the FIERCE results show. This is the case of Spain where many public servants in the Ministry of Equality are or have been active in the feminist movement. In other contexts, the political system creates significant barriers for developing feminist democratic innovations. Among the examined case studies, this was notably the case in Poland and Turkey where activists involved in the FIERCE Actions faced direct resistance. As mentioned in chapter 3, the workshop initially planned in Gardeja, Poland, was cancelled following the withdrawal of municipal support (see

Section 3.3.1.), while the organisers of the “Women's Rights to Work” Action in Turkey encountered difficulties in securing an independent space for their activities. Thus, this key factor about the role of the political system is undoubtedly most challenging for feminist movements in countries where governments have adopted anti-feminist/anti-gender views and policies.

Political context matters for the possibilities of developing feminist democratic innovations, but more importantly feminist movements’ agency and transformative approach to institutional relations can also challenge embedded structures and approach institutions without being ‘inside’ or ‘outside’. In this sense, feminist movements can evolve with shifting political circumstances by remaining open to new possibilities and opportunities, embracing hybrid activism instead of holding on to rigid positions.

5.1.4. The Role of Emotions

Expressing and sharing emotions within activist settings constitute an innovative practice in political contexts where relational and emotional forms of expression and communication are systematically devalued in favour of the norms of ‘rational argumentation’ (Martínez-Palacios 2017). Emotions, in this sense, are today essential to feminist democratic innovation. They underscore that feminist approaches to democratic politics interrogate and challenge not only the content of politics (the “what”), but also the ways in which political issues and conflicts are articulated and contested (the “how”).

The FIERCE material and co-creation activities (Labs, Actions, and the empirical streams) provide several examples of how contemporary feminist movements foster alternative practices of emotionality, both in activist spaces and in public outreach/communication. One example is the FIERCE Action of the Centre for Violence Prevention in Denmark that mobilized support for victims of gender-based violence by creating artistic artifacts based on their stories, which were then displayed in a public exhibition. Similarly, the "Survive the Borderlands" project by the activist groups Boat Collective and Musafir in Greece aims to restore visibility to migrant stories by drawing on their collective memory and performing their narratives in public. This example shows how memory provide an important resource in highlighting experiences of injustice in public and invoking complex emotions in feminist campaigns.

In terms of feminist democratic innovation as experimentation within movements, emotions are essential to establish spaces for care and mutual support, particularly when activists risk burnout or are targeted by repressive politics. This is, for example, the case in the Feminist Night March campaign in Turkey where activists, drawing on ideas of collective empowerment, celebrate unity and togetherness within feminism and rehearse positive emotions such as excitement, laughter, joy, hope, and determination. In the Labs and FIERCE Action in Turkey, activists frequently referred to a poster capturing: “If you despair, remember this crowd”, which was brought by an anonymous woman to the 2020 Istanbul feminist night-march. At the same time, it has also been crucial for many feminist activists to provide space for the articulation of ‘negative’ emotions such as feelings of guilt associated with

holding power and resources – a concern that was also expressed by academics and institutional partners when reflecting on their positions in relation to the invited activists in the Labs and the Actions.

Feminist movements insist on making space for emotions and giving visibility to emotional dimensions as an integral part of their political actions and processes of feminist democratic innovation. The results from the co-creation processes facilitated by the FIERCE project highlight the productive role of what can be called as “dual emotionality”, i.e., the interplay between hope/joy and frustration/anger, which allows to make room for the full scale of emotions, not only of emotions labelled as positive.

5.2. Recommendations for Feminist Research and Practice

Based on the analysis of National Labs, FIERCE Actions, and interviews, as well as critical discussions of the findings, this deliverable highlights a multiplicity of distinct forms and many concrete examples of feminist democratic innovation across Europe, testifying to a revitalization of feminist movements in recent years. To conclude, we provide four essential recommendations for feminist research and practice based on our in-depth inquiry into feminist democratic innovations.

- *Continuous attention to intersectionality and the (re)production of internal power dynamics in feminist democratic innovations.* This requires, e.g., rethinking established habits and ways to go about, such as reconsidering the locality of activities since the predominately urbanized character of organizing often makes it more difficult for people in the periphery to participate. Similarly, it requires constant questioning of the truly intersectional nature of participation, establishing alliances, and expanding movements and networks to different minoritised groups rather than only including the ‘usual suspects,’ since the feminist subject cannot be completely determined in advance. Addressing power inequalities and being attentive to intersectional forms of participation are necessary aspects of creating and maintaining safe and constructive spaces of experimentation with feminist democratic innovations.
- *Securing the resources needed to sustain feminist democratic innovations in time and space.* Resource gaps affect internal dynamics within movements and networks as well as the potential for creative public outreach, production and circulation of feminist knowledge, alliance-building, and inclusive mobilization efforts which are all part of the core practices of feminist democratic innovation. Strengthening these aspects about securing funding to support feminist research, practice and activism is necessary for deepening democracy, recalling that the aim of feminist democratic innovation is precisely to ensure equality, intersectional justice, and space for minority voices (Caravantes & Lombardo, 2024). In light of the FIERCE experiences, the EU funding programmes combining research and action-oriented component should consider redesigning the financial aspects of funding to recognize and support the crucial role of external participants (such as activists) in innovative and inclusive research.

- *Active use of hybridity in rethinking and reenacting feminist activist practices.* Hybrid activism moves beyond dichotomic categories, and shares with intersectionality a fundamental openness to whatever, or whomever, is not immediately identifiable through established categories and traditional ways of organizing democratic politics and activism. This form of open exploration resonates with Fominaya's claim that social movements can develop "fuzzy democratic imaginaries", challenging classical models of politics and policymaking through an open mode of experimentation where the image of what democracy implies is more 'fuzzy' than fixed (2022). This recommendation also aligns with Coccia et al.'s proposal to conceive ambivalence as a feminist project in the sense that ambivalence can challenge old binaries, find value in uncertainty, and alert us to the presence of conflicting emotions (2024). Ambivalence is, in Donna Haraway's phrasing, thereby about "staying with the trouble" (2016). Feminist movements should 'stay within the trouble' and through hybrid and intersectional forms of activism challenge traditional, dichotomous categorizations in their exploration and deepening of feminist democratic innovations.
- *Critical reflection on the ambivalence of democratic innovation itself.* Democracy is not easily defined or practiced and, according to some theorists, it requires innovation to persist. Democratic innovation is also often an ambivalent practice since it is not always evident what the purpose of innovation is, and whether the celebratory tone about being innovative is more a façade sustained by powerholders benefiting from a political system that does not substantially change. In this respect, optimism and hope about innovation discourse must be complemented with critical reflection on which distinct purpose a certain innovation is supposed to have, and whether some forms of political innovation might actually contain antidemocratic and antifeminist elements. What is distinct about *feminist* democratic innovations, however, is that democratic practices are being developed and evaluated with reference to feminist principles about equality and solidarity, adding a normative dimension that most often also entails self-critique.

The report highlights the need for revitalization and experimentation within the feminist movement in Europe to spur and sustain democratic innovation. This is particularly urgent in times of crisis and attacks on feminism and gender equality and, consequently, on democracy. For democratic innovation to take shape, it requires awareness at all levels of policy and practice, attention to power dynamics and inequalities, and a sustained support for feminist contributions. This includes advancing intersectional solidarity, practices, and demands, with the ultimate aim of deepening and strengthening democracy through the promotion of inclusive, gendered, and intersectional processes of participation and mobilization.

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